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MAKE IN INDIA - A GLOBAL MANUFACTURING HUB

Abstract: *This research paper aims to identify some of the key challenges in the path of development and recommend possible solutions to deal with the same. This paper has been able to identify the following major challenges in the path of making India a global manufacturing hub and accordingly make a few suggestions regarding possible solutions to deal with each of the issues: Improving the ease of doing business in India, Improving the employability of general and engineering graduates, Infrastructure development of major roads and highways in the country, Capacity addition in the power sector to meet industrial energy demand. It is to be noted that the above list is not exhaustive and there are lot of other ample challenges towards making India a global manufacturing hub. However, focusing on these issues and taking adequate measures to deal with the same will go a long way towards turning the "Make in India" vision into a dream come true.*

Keywords: *global, manufacturing, hub, Infrastructure, development.*

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СДЕЛАТЬ В ИНДИИ - ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫЙ ЦЕНТР

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Аннотация: Данная исследовательская работа направлена на выявление некоторых ключевых проблем на пути развития и рекомендации возможных вариантов для их решения. В этом документе удалось выявить следующие основные проблемы на пути превращения Индии в глобальный производственный центр и, соответственно, внести несколько предложений относительно возможных решений для решения каждой из проблем: повышение удобства ведения бизнеса в Индии, улучшение возможностей трудоустройства выпускников общего и инженерного профиля, развитие инфраструктуры основных дорог и автомагистралей в стране, увеличение мощностей в энергетическом секторе для удовлетворения промышленного спроса на энергию. Следует отметить, что приведенный выше список не является исчерпывающим, и существует множество других серьезных проблем на пути превращения Индии в глобальный производственный центр. Однако сосредоточение внимания на этих проблемах и принятие адекватных мер для их решения будет иметь большое значение для превращения концепции "Сделать в Индии" в воплощение мечты.

Ключевые слова: глобальный, производство, хаб, инфраструктура, развитие.

Introduction

That day, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi addressed an audience of 500 domestic and international entrepreneurs in New Delhi, in an atmosphere charged with euphoria following the success of India's first mission to Mars the previous day. Modi inaugurated a campaign aimed at transforming India into a global manufacturing hub and at easing its business climate for both domestic and foreign investors. A logo, a portal and brochures detailing 25 priority sectors were introduced that day. The logo shows a striding lion made of cogs with the campaign name across its body.

The stock market boom at the clear mandate given to BJP in the 2014 Lok Sabha elections and the current stock market scenario was a clear indicator of investor confidence in the Narendra Modi Government. Further steps by Mr. Modi like the "Make in India" and "Digital India" campaigns, invitation to the leaders of all the SAARC countries, US and Japan visit and various business friendly reforms have significantly created a positive business environment in the country.

However, there are certain bottlenecks in the economy which the Government needs to address towards making India a global manufacturing hub. This research paper aims to analyze the key issues facing the "Make in India" vision and recommend possible strategies to deal with the same.

Discussion

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Recent policy measures and projects to open up India's manufacturing sector are:

- 100 % Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) allowed in the telecom sector;
- 100 % FDI in single-brand retail;
- Validity of industrial license extended to three years;
- For all non-risk, non-hazardous businesses, a system of self-certification to be introduced;
- Process of obtaining environmental clearances made online.
- The Government of India is developing the Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor (DMIC) as a global manufacturing and an investment destination utilising the 1,483 km-long, highcapacity western Dedicated Railway Freight Corridor (DFC) as the backbone.

FDI is defined as an investment in which the investor acquire a substantial controlling interest in a foreign industry. FDI involves ownership and/or control of the company abroad (Markusen, Melvin, Kaempler, and Maskus, 1995). FDI is driving the process of globalization by creating an increasingly tighter global production network. Many countries experiences good economic growth through FDI (Manning and Shea, 1989), such as FDI in developing countries (includes Latin America, Asia and Central and Eastern Europe) made a comeback in about 1994 (Krugman and Obstfeld, 1997; Han, 2004).

FDI flows as one of financing type in investment is expected to boost economy growth. FDI serves as a catalyst for rapid economic growth by enabling developing countries to leapfrog developmental stages and to catch up with advanced economies, it constitutes also an important advocate for improved social norms. In this respect, FDI plays a major role in the larger development agenda of the host countries. Two of the main social aspects of development i.e. employment and environment Nevertheless, the ultimate impact of FDI on domestic economic growth depends on the diffusion of best practice through the local economy at large. This diffusion process takes place through four main channels, i.e. backward linkages with local suppliers (sourcing), forward linkages with local producers and distributors, horizontal linkages with local competitors, and linkages with local institutions such as universities and research institutes as well as vocational training centers. To developing countries, the most important channel of these is usually sourcing, i.e. the purchase of inputs and services from local instead of foreign suppliers.

FDI flows to where fast economic growth has been recorded. A virtuous circle is observed here: at same time that FDI contributes significantly to economic growth, faster economic growth attracts more FDI because it increases foreign investors' confidence in the economy, which in turn pushes the growth rate even higher. In the

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least developed countries, studies have shown that FDI in fact follows, not proceeds, some initial growth or at least the promise of growth.

Additional Reasons for the New Initiative

Several pressing issues prompted the launch of this campaign. First and foremost, India needs to reboot its economy. After several years of gross national product (GNP) growth averaging 7.7%, between 2002 and 2011, this pace slowed down to around 5% in 2013 and 2014. India began the calendar year 2021 with an economy undergoing a deep recession as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the IMF and other leading international organizations, production in the country decreased by 8% in mid-2020 and by 10% in October of the same year¹. In 2020/2021 fin. year (fiscal year in India from April 1 of the current year to March 31 of the next year) The country's GDP shrank by an estimated 7.7%. The decline in industrial production and services amounted to 9.6% and 8.8%, respectively. Weak signs of economic recovery emerged only at the end of 2020. - GDP growth was 0.4%, thus marking the country's exit from the technical recession.

India's GDP grew 20,1 percent in the second quarter from last year, slightly in line with economists' forecasts of 21 percent growth. The report of the Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation showed that in the second quarter, growth was observed in various sectors of the economy. In trade, hotel and transport sectors, it amounted to 34,3 percent, in construction – 68,3 percent. The agro-industrial complex grew by 4,5 percent, the industrial complex - by 49,6 percent. The Indian rupee climbed to a peak since May and stocks hit new highs².

Economic growth remained at 9.2 percent of GDP forecast for 2021, becoming the fastest among major economies, surpassing the 8.5 percent growth mark in China. High rates of coronavirus vaccinations have allowed people to live their lives as usual and reduce damage in services, and production figures were higher than expected, which contributed to record growth rates.

Second, India needs more jobs for its young people. Recently, on average, 5 million new jobs have been created each year, but around 12 million people join the workforce each year. This is the other side of the demographic dividend: India's labour force is expected to grow to 600 million by 2022. Job creation will fight poverty and help divert people from agriculture, which has a low capacity to sustain their livelihood.

¹ <https://scroll.in/author/8>

² <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-08-31/resilient-demand-keeps-india-on-track-to-world-s-fastest-growth?srnd=economics-vp>

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Third, India's economic development model has been quite peculiar, offering privileges to skilled labour often employed by foreign companies. Conversely, other economies have achieved success by first providing incentives for job-creating manufacturing industries. That is why today manufacturing in China makes up 34% of gross domestic product. The Chinese have positioned themselves as the 'workshop' of the world, accounting for 22.4% of global manufacturing, while India accounts for only 2%. India's manufacturing sector is less productive compared to its competitors and accounts for only 15% of its GDP. The government has set a target of 25% of GDP by 2022.

Reaction to “Make in India”

“Make in India” has received widespread support from industry leaders from both India and abroad as well as from the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII). Some companies, including foreign ones, have already announced plans related to the initiative. Reserve Bank of India Governor Raghuram Rajan dismissed the idea of introducing a policy targeting the manufacturing sector, just because it had worked for China, given how different the two countries are. He underlined the risks of an export-driven approach in a global economy still in crisis, and where many industrialized economies are strengthening their own manufacturing capabilities. “The world as a whole is unlikely to be able to accommodate another export-led China”, he said.

C. K. Ranganathan, the founding chairman of popular Indian household brand CavinKare, said that he would rather support a “Made in India” approach in which India would be creating its own internationally renowned brands. Srikant Jena, a former government minister, stated that efforts to resolve caste and gender inequalities as well as regional imbalances were missing from the initiative.

Conclusion

Although the ease of doing business score went down to 142 from 134 last year, the World Bank has taken care to distance this downslide from the NDA government which took charge barely a week earlier and World Bank has used data till May 2019 whereas most measures to improve doing business were undertaken subsequent to that. The various measures undertaken by the NDA Government to address issues related to economic growth, delay in Government decisions and reforms in the Labour law, Land law and taxation have kick started the manufacturing sector and shot the GDP growth by 5.7 % in the last quarter.

The Modi Government has also signed a staggering USD 35 Billion investment deal with Japan for infrastructure development.

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If governance continues in the current manner, we can definitely hope to see significant and sustainable growth in the manufacturing sector and progress towards India becoming a Global manufacturing hub.

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BIOECONOMICS, NEUROECONOMICS AND NEUROMARKETING: NEW APPROACHES TO CUSTOMERS AND BUSINESSES

Abstract: *New approaches that integrate several disciplines such as economics, biology, psychology, neuroscience etc. are considered appropriate for providing better explanation of economic events and complex economies of today. Bioeconomics, originated from the synthesis of economics and biology, intends to explain economic events using a biological basis and vice versa and this discipline is important to the protection of environment and life support system. Bio-economic modeling provides the assessment of the impacts of environmental management changes based on evaluation of the costs and benefits linked with environmental resource usage and it determines the optimal level of resource extraction to maximize*

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economic profits. Neuroeconomics is a natural extension of bioeconomics focusing on behavioral dispositions and behavioral patterns of evolutionary processes. Neuromarketing crosses traditional boundaries between neuroscience, neuroeconomics and marketing research. The aim of the paper is to provide a theoretical framework for bioeconomics, neuroeconomics and neuromarketing based on the recent empirical studies and describes different techniques used in these new progressive approaches.

Keywords: *bioeconomics, decision-making, neuroeconomics, neuromarketing.*

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БИОЭКОНОМИКА, НЕЙРОЭКОНОМИКА И НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГ: НОВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К КЛИЕНТАМ И БИЗНЕСУ

Аннотация: *Новые подходы, объединяющие несколько дисциплин, таких как экономика, биология, психология, нейробиология и т.д., считаются подходящими для лучшего объяснения экономических событий и сложных экономик сегодняшнего дня. Биоэкономика, возникшая из синтеза экономики и биологии, призвана объяснять экономические события с использованием биологической основы и наоборот, и эта дисциплина важна для защиты окружающей среды и системы жизнеобеспечения. Биоэкономическое моделирование обеспечивает оценку последствий изменений в управлении окружающей средой на основе оценки затрат и выгод, связанных с использованием экологических ресурсов, и определяет оптимальный уровень добычи ресурсов для максимизации экономической прибыли. Нейроэкономика является естественным продолжением биоэкономики, фокусирующейся на поведенческих установках и поведенческих моделях эволюционных процессов. Нейромаркетинг пересекает традиционные границы между нейронаукой, нейроэкономикой и маркетинговыми исследованиями. Цель статьи - дать теоретическую основу для биоэкономики, нейроэкономики и нейромаркетинга на основе недавних эмпирических исследований и описать различные методы, используемые в этих новых прогрессивных подходах.*

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Ключевые слова: *биоэкономика, принятие решений, нейроэкономика, нейромаркетинг.*

Introduction

New approaches that integrate several disciplines such as economics, biology, psychology, neuroscience etc. are considered to provide better explanation of economic events and complex economies of today. Economic concept based on biological materials and resources is aimed to create the economy with low emissions in line with requirements of sustainable agriculture and fisheries, food safety and better utilization of renewable energy for industrial processes in ensuring biodiversity and environmental protection. Another new approach in comparison to conventional economic theory is neuroeconomics that studies the impact of emotional, social, psychological and other factors on the various economic decisions and explains the principles of decision-making process and behavioural strategies of consumers based on the neurobiological and psychological aspects. Additionally, marketing theory and practice use the application of neuroscience for better understanding of consumer choice and for influencing consumers' behaviour.

The paper provides a theoretical framework for bioeconomics, neuroeconomics and neuromarketing based on the recent empirical research and describes different techniques used in these new progressive approaches.

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Methods

The main aim of the paper is to summarize and discuss the key topics: bioeconomics, neuroeconomics and neuromarketing and to provide an overview of the research techniques and models used in these fields. Recently published international literature dealing with the selected topic has been examined. In order to fulfill the main aim, the comparative method is used for comparing the researcher's opinions on the chosen disciplines and for explaining differences between neuroeconomics and neuromarketing.

Result and Discussion

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Nowadays, a new and more central role is given to the more sustainable direction of the development of the economy based on the production and usage of biological resources (forestry, fisheries, agriculture, biomass-based industries etc.). [Sundar, 2012] explains that the traditional branch of economics does not link economics with biology, however, a progressive branch of social science called bioeconomics, originated from the synthesis of economics and biology, intends to explain economic events using a biological basis and vice versa. More specifically, it is a change in the development of the economy-environment disciplines such as natural resource economics, environmental economics and ecological economics. Bioeconomics is important to the protection of environment and life support system. The health status of the people can be increased by the production of goods and services through bio-economic method that develops green products and promotes green consumerism. Furthermore, the economics knowledge on utilization of biological resource is needed for achieving sustainable development.

[Boncoeur and Thebaud, 2011] point out that the interaction of biological and economic processes is represented by bio-economic model and it is usually made up of three components: Biological component describes the bio-ecological processes at work; Technical component describes the way human activities interact with the bio-ecological processes; Economic component describes the results of these activities in term of (market or non-market) costs, benefits and the consequences of these results on human behaviour. Bio-economic modeling provides the assessment of the impacts of environmental management changes based on evaluation of the costs and benefits linked with environmental resource usage and it determines the optimal level of resource extraction to maximize economic profits. Various bio-economic models have been developed and tested on different farming systems and under heterogeneous agro-ecological conditions; for example, bio-econometric modeling of fisheries are used to determine the optimal levels of effort under different fisheries management regimes (harvest levels, season length etc.). Agro-economic models predict the impact of changes in environmental resources (water and soil quality etc.) on agricultural production and the following approaches could be used for bioeconomic modelling of agricultural systems: accounting (descriptive book-keeping systems e.g. gross margin analysis), regression (statistical estimates of site-, or region-specific agro-economic production functions based on observed relationships between prices, farm inputs, policies, and physical characteristics of the land) and mathematical programming aimed to optimise and simulate the optimal demand for environmental inputs that maximise farm profits depending on input/output prices, available capital or labour and environmental conditions (e.g. MIDAS). In case of forest models, mathematical programming to maximise net present value of forest biomass volume or Faustmann

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Pressler-Ohlin model for determination of optimal rotation age maximising net present value of timber production for a forest stand are used [Kragt, 2012].

[J.J., 2007] claims that neuroeconomics is a natural extension of bioeconomics focusing also on behavioral dispositions and behavioral patterns of evolutionary processes. Neuroeconomics identifies evolved mechanisms and processes that are at work in decision-making at the neural level of the brain. [Vlasceanu, 2014] states that neuroeconomics and neuromarketing are new emerging interdisciplinary fields that offer a new vision of the decision-making process and both are established on various disciplines and have borrowed a number of methods, techniques and tools of neuroscience.; neuroeconomics is based on e.g. neuroscience, economics, mathematics, statistics and cognitive sciences and neuromarketing is based on fields such as neuroscience, economics and psychology. Neuroeconomics focuses on the activity of our brains when we are in the evaluation process of reward (decision making process about money) or fear e.g. if we calculate risks. [Neumarker, 2007] points out that neuroeconomists believe that the study of neural mechanism behind human decision-making process is essential for finding right and unique decision mechanism for the accurate prediction of behaviour and economic outcomes. Neuroeconomics rediscovers the research of the classical contributors to the economic theory of human behavior by adding and specifying important components of human behavior (many of which are ignored in standard economics), by arguing on the unity of behavioural sciences and by drawn the economist's attention to the brain processes of human decision-making. Furthermore, neuroeconomics discover final causes of human decision-making together with bioeconomic studies. According to [Bickel, 2006], the brain function can be examined in decision making and choice by brain imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) or position emission tomography (PET). These techniques determine areas of relative brain activation, and deduce the specific portions of brain used during decision making tasks in various circumstances (e.g. under uncertainty, in social situations). Functional magnetic resonance imaging is non-invasive method and it works due to different magnetic properties of oxyhemoglobin and deoxyhemoglobin. For example, Montague et al. examine neuronal responses associated with preferences for soft drinks by performing fMRI. Subjects are more likely to prefer Coke over Pepsi during informed testing in comparison to blind testing, and this preference is reflected in increased neuronal activation in brain regions assumed to be involved in reward. This research makes clear the neuronal underpinnings of brand effects, which can strongly influence consumer choices [Braeutigam, 2005].

“Neuromarketing is a recent interdisciplinary field which crosses traditional boundaries between neuroscience, neuroeconomics and marketing research” say

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[Ulman and Yildiz, 2015]. [Hubert, 2010] explains that neuromarketing is a consumer neuroscience and a sub-area of neuroeconomics that investigates marketing-relevant problems. The discipline provides better understanding of how unconscious mind processing influences the decision to purchase and it helps to understand the consumers' thoughts, emotions, feelings, needs and motivation in relation to the marketing products. Neuromarketing could also help buyers and marketing experts to understand each other better, but also to understand better the products they want, which leads to a win/win situation for both sides [Wilson, 2008]. Häusel (as cited in [Gentner, 2012]) describes the possibilities of neuromarketing as follows:

Understanding of the unconscious decision-making processes and neural mechanisms; Identification of the various emotional systems in the human brain and investigation of their functions;

- Research of how various channels of perception can be used effectively; Analysis of the attention and cognitive processes in the brain;
- Optimization of text and language; Identification of certain consumer types and their better and more successful segmentation;
- Determination of effects of differences in thinking style, emotional structure and behavior for marketing purposes;
- Development of effective and efficient strategies in order to reach aging consumers.

[Javor, 2013] consider neuromarketing as a term often used in the media in recent years, however, on-going debate have been focused on potential ethical aspects and the public fear of negative consequences for society, more specifically for consumers. Nevertheless, other researchers and journalists believe that neuromarketing is considered to be beneficial for consumers due to the fact that it would lead to product improvement. Therefore, authors warn that it is important to distinguish academic studies using neuroscientific methods with focus on the consumer's point of view from commercial marketing aimed to apply findings in order to sell product. Additionally, neuromarketing research techniques (represented by electroencephalography, magnetoencephalography, functional magnetic resonance imaging, eyetracking glasses and the galvanic-skin response) are essential for gathering valuable insights in connection with the neural substrates of emotional intelligence and allow researchers to seize short-lived interaction between different brain structures during the decision making process [Pop, 2013]. More specifically, the electroencephalography (EEG) belong to the most widespread instruments aimed to measure brainwaves' activity and it helps to understand the way the brain responds to various stimuli, say [Pradeep, 2010]. Lewis (as cited in [Krajnovic, 2012]) considers EEG method to be the most practical, the most cost-effective and the most suitable among the currently developed

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methods while taking into consideration the simplicity of use and compactness of the apparatus. The functional magnetic resonance imaging measures the increase of the oxygen level in the brain's blood flow; magnetoencephalography records the magnet fields generated by the brain's electrical activity and it helps to notice changes in the brain's electrical activity; and eye tracking is aimed to observe the way the print influences the subject's attention and cognitive processing.

[Breiter, 2015] explain differences between neuroeconomics and neuromarketing. Neuroeconomics generally explains how the individuals make their choices and represents distribution of choices. There are four steps in the process of making a choice (Figure 1 (A)). On the other hand, neuromarketing focuses on how individuals and groups can be shifted or altered from one pattern of decisions to another pattern, or to change their distribution of choices. One potential model for the effect of influence on behaviour is shown in Figure 1 (B) where influence can be considered the difference in gradients for preference inside a person and outside a person and behaviour feeds back onto these internal and external gradients of preference as experienced utility of expressed behaviour.

Figure 1: Comparison of neuroeconomics and neuromarketing.

Conclusion

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The paper presented recent findings from studies of bioeconomics, neuroeconomics and neuromarketing with the emphasis on their features, techniques and models for gathering valuable outcomes. A progressive branch of social science called bioeconomics, originated from the synthesis of economics and biology, intends to explain economic events using a biological basis and vice versa. Various bio-economic models have been developed and tested on different farming systems and under heterogeneous agro-ecological conditions e.g. bio-economic modelling of fisheries, forest and agro-economic models. Neuroeconomics is a natural extension of bioeconomics and it explains how the individuals make their choices and represents distribution of choices. On the other hand, neuromarketing focuses on how individuals and groups can be shifted from one pattern of decisions to another pattern, or to change their distribution of choices. Neuroeconomics uses brain imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging or position emission tomography to explore brain function in decision making and choice. Electroencephalography, magnetoencephalography, functional magnetic resonance imaging, eye-tracking glasses and the galvanic-skin response belong to the neuromarketing research techniques that are essential for understanding short-lived interaction between different brain structures during the decision-making process.

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THE PROBLEMS OF ASSESSING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESSES

Abstract: *Entrepreneurship, as an independent socio-economic phenomenon with deep historical roots and a long path of evolutionary development, has proved its high efficiency, its ability to qualitatively transform the entire set of economic and social processes, to give them an innovative impulse. The success of the development of small businesses largely depends on the level of their competitiveness. Therefore, this concept acquires a decisive meaning, both for individual enterprises or groups of enterprises, and directly affects the situation in a particular region and the country as a whole. The article considers approaches to various methods of determining the competitiveness of small businesses, their disadvantages and advantages are studied. The definition of competitiveness of business entities is substantiated.*

Keywords: *business, intensification, competitiveness, market competitiveness, competitiveness factors, processing of competitiveness indicators.*

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ПРОБЛЕМАТИКА ОЦЕНКА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ СУБЪЕКТОВ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА

Аннотация: *Предпринимательство, как самостоятельное социально-экономическое явление, имеющие глубокие исторические корни и прошедшее*

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длительный путь эволюционного развития, доказало свою высокую эффективность, свою способность к качественным преобразованиям всей совокупности экономических и социальных процессов, к приданию им инновационного импульса. Успешность развития субъектов малого предпринимательства в значительной мере зависит от уровня их конкурентоспособности. Поэтому данное понятие приобретает определяющее значение, как для отдельных предприятий или групп предприятий, так и непосредственно влияет на ситуацию в отдельном регионе и стране в целом. В статье рассмотрены подходы к различным методикам определения конкурентоспособности субъектов малого предпринимательства, изучены их недостатки и преимущества. Обосновано определение конкурентоспособности субъектов предпринимательства.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, интенсификация, конкурентоспособность, рыночная конкурентоспособность, факторы конкурентоспособности, обработка показателей конкурентоспособности.

For the national economy of Uzbekistan, enhancing competitiveness of businesses is one of the most important strategic objectives, the solution of which depends on economic growth, business development, the welfare of the population and the possibility of effective integration of the country's economy into the world economic system, which is changing rapidly in the context of economic globalization. Scientists, practitioners and international financial institutions note low competitiveness of domestic business entities. Problems of competitiveness increase objectively acquire priority character in economic science. If quite recently there was an opinion that this task can be solved at the micro-level by the enterprises themselves, being guided by objective laws of the market, now there comes an understanding of necessity to develop a competitiveness increase strategy at the state level taking into account institutional conditions of state development as a whole.

Winning the competition for economic wellbeing and survival is the ultimate goal for an entrepreneur. It is the result of systematic and competent efforts of a firm to improve the competitiveness of its products and services and the competitiveness of itself.

The success of development of small business entities to a great extent depends on the level of their competitiveness. Therefore, this concept acquires a decisive importance both for individual enterprises and directly affects the situation in the region and the country as a whole.

A distinction is made between competitiveness of goods and services, business entities (entrepreneurship), regions, industries and countries (national economy as a whole). There is a close relationship between all these levels: country, regional and sectoral competitiveness ultimately depends on the ability of particular producers to

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produce competitive goods. Product competitiveness is thus a basic category for all other levels of competitiveness.

In our opinion, the competitiveness of goods should be defined as a degree of attractiveness of goods for consumers, determining the potential and real possibility to satisfy their needs. At the same time, product competitiveness is a necessary but not sufficient condition for the competitiveness of an enterprise structure. The enterprise can produce competitive products, but not be competitive.

There are the following main differences between the concepts of product competitiveness and small business enterprise (SME):

- The buyer is the main evaluator of competitiveness of goods and small business entity. However, unlike product competitiveness assessment, small business entity competitiveness is also assessed by the manufacturer itself, determining the expediency of producing a specific type of goods under specific conditions.
- The assessment of product competitiveness applies to each specific type of product, while SME competitiveness covers the entire nomenclature and assortment, as well as all types of production and economic activities carried out by SMEs (financial, investment activities, etc.);
- An important parameter for evaluating the competitiveness of goods and small business entities is their life cycle. When the subject of the study is an ongoing assessment of competitiveness, the time factor is of no particular importance. When it comes to the assessment of competitiveness for a long-term period, it should be taken into account that the life cycle of small business entity, as a rule, is longer. The product range may change several times during the period of the manufacturer's operation.

Consequently, we can conclude that the concept of SME competitiveness is more complex and integral, i.e., it includes a much larger number of key elements than product competitiveness.

Taking into account all the above, the author gives the following definition: SME competitiveness is a comprehensive characteristic that makes it possible to assess the results of its activities and reflects its potential and ability at any time to ensure its competitive advantages and profitability, as well as to adapt to the constantly changing conditions of the external environment.

Thus, market competitiveness of business entities in the structure of the national economy of Uzbekistan from the position of macro-analysis can be defined as the ability of entrepreneurs in the present and in the future to produce and sell goods on the national and global markets that are more attractive in price and quality than those of foreign or domestic competitors. The study of competitors and competitive conditions in an industry is required by a business entity primarily in order to determine its advantages and disadvantages over its competitors and to draw conclusions for developing its own

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successful competitive strategy and maintaining its competitive advantage. In any case, the assessment of the competitiveness of the enterprise has the following objective: to determine the position of the enterprise in the market under study.

In our opinion, none of the existing approaches to assessing the competitiveness of enterprises has found wide application in the practice of economic analysis. This allows us to conclude that there is currently no universal methodology for a comprehensive assessment of enterprise competitiveness.

In addition to private drawbacks, the analysis of the existing approaches allows us to note the following general drawbacks of the presented methods. The vast majority of methods are based on identifying the factors determining the competitiveness of business entities, with an emphasis on identifying the maximum number of these factors, creating their exhaustive list. Further, the identified factors are processed by means of various mathematical methods.

However, the system of small business entity competitiveness factors is open, and the set of elements of this system is fuzzy. Indeed, when assessing the labor resources of the small business entity, one can conclude that labor efficiency depends on the psycho-physiological well-being of workers, and thus, including the level of divorce in a particular locality. Considering the small business entity production capabilities, we come to the conclusion about the dependence of the small business entity technological potential on the level of funding of scientific programs in a given state, and hence the degree of filling the budget. Similarly (when deeper analysis leads to an enormous increase in the number of factors) is the case in all areas of SME research: finances, production and economic potential, labor resources, competitive environment, and so on. It can be argued that, ultimately, the entire set of random and regular elementary events occurring in the space under study has a greater or lesser impact on the competitiveness of small business entity (Tab. 1).

Table 1: Characteristics of methods for assessing the competitiveness of small businesses

Method	Essence of the method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Matrix	Analysis of the matrix: horizontally - growth (reduction) of sales volume;	The availability of information on sales volumes and relative market shares of competitors	It eliminates the analysis of the causes of what is happening and complicates the development of management decisions

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	vertically - relative market share of the enterprise.	allows the method to ensure high adequacy of estimation.	and requires reliable marketing information.
Method based on the theory of effective competition	The most competitive enterprises are those where the work of all departments and services is best organized.	Accounting for the very diverse aspects of an enterprise.	The sum of the individual elements of a complex system, which is any enterprise, does not give the same result as the system as a whole.
Method based on assessment of product competitiveness	The higher the competitiveness of an enterprise is, the higher is the competitiveness of its products.	It takes into account one of the most important components of enterprise competitiveness - competitiveness of its products.	The competitiveness of an enterprise takes the form of product competitiveness and does not affect other aspects of its activities.
Integrated	Enterprise competitiveness is an integral value in relation to current competitiveness and competitive potential.	It takes into account not only the achieved level of competitiveness of the enterprise, but also its possible dynamics in the future.	The specific methods and techniques used in determining current and potential competitiveness ultimately replicate those used in the approaches discussed earlier.

Thus, the number of competitiveness factors is almost infinite, hence, no matter how extensive their list is, it will still not be exhaustive, and hence, based on such an incomplete list, the assessment of enterprise competitiveness will be inadequate.

As a result, all the existing lists of competitiveness factors are very tentative, which does not allow their use for assessing the competitiveness of enterprises. The

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limited list determines the limitedness of the method. At the same time, the excessive increase in the number of competitiveness factors leads to the fact that the labor intensity of their mathematical processing becomes extremely high, and the task of collecting the necessary data - practically impossible, which significantly reduces the practical applicability of such methods for assessing the competitiveness of enterprises.

To evaluate the factors of competitiveness identified by researchers, as well as to determine a number of other indicators, approximate, approximate estimates, "expert methods" are used, suffering from significant subjectivity and conditionality. Of course, in some cases it is impossible to avoid such an approach, but the use of such estimates as a basic method leads to a very weak mathematical connection of the initial conditional factors with the assessed indicator of competitiveness.

We believe that a number of techniques in assessing the competitiveness of enterprises are based on very complex idealized constructions: new definitions and indicators for economic science are introduced, various matrices are built, new coordinate systems are introduced, and so on. Although the logical validity of the theoretical models used is not in doubt, these models appear as very abstract in the specific economic conditions of a particular economic entity. Certain criticism is caused by the reduction of multi-dimensional and heterogeneous indicators (for example, the level of labor productivity and probability of bankruptcy of the enterprise) into a single indicator of competitiveness of the economic entity. Here economists introduce coefficients determining the weighting value of each of the evaluated factors, and at the same time bringing in order the dimensionality of the indicators. However, the coefficients used in most cases are very conditional, which entails the inadequacy of assessing the impact of certain factors on the competitiveness of the enterprise. But the matter is not only in the conventionality of weighting coefficients. As it was shown earlier, different economic factors in each specific economic situation to a different extent influence the competitiveness of different enterprises, therefore, it is inadequate to knowingly establish uniform weight coefficients for assessing the competitiveness of various economic entities.

Thus, we can conclude - the definition of enterprise competitiveness is an integral element of any business entity, in order to:

- development of measures to improve competitiveness;
- selection of counterparties for joint activities;
- drawing up a program for the enterprise's entry into new markets;
- of carrying out investment activities;
- implementation of state regulation of the economy.

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QR-Article

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MODERN GLOBAL TENDENCIES OF STOCK MARKET DEVELOPMENT

Abstract: *Progressive growth scales of world equity market is provided under influence of modern worldwide tendencies among which there is reduction of the share of commercial banks in financial assets and the growth of the share intuitions of equity market and institutional investors; substantial change of the structure of financial tools of the market for benefit of real sector; strengthening interrelation between financial and real sectors of economy; further concentration and realization of funds; the process of securitization; rise of the role and importance of individual investors in equity market; globalization and internationalization of equity market.*

Keywords: *Centralization, Concentration of funds, financial tools, stock market, globalization of equity market, individual investors, institutional investors, securitization.*

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ФОНД БОЗОРИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ГЛОБАЛ ТЕНДЕНЦИЯЛАРИ

Аннотация: *Жаҳон қимматли қозғалар бозорининг прогрессив ўсиш миқёси замонавий жаҳон тенденциялари таъсири остида таъминланади, улар орасида тижорат банкларининг молиявий активлардаги улушининг камайиши*

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ва қимматли қозғалар бозори ва институционал инвесторларнинг улуш интуицияларининг ўсиши кузатилмоқда; реал сектор манфаати учун бозорнинг молиявий воситалари тузилмасини сезиларли даражада ўзгартириши; иқтисодиётнинг молиявий ва реал секторлари ўртасидаги ўзаро алоқани мустаҳкамлаш; маблағларни янада жамлаш ва реализация қилиши; тижорат банкларининг қимматли; қимматли қозғалар бозорида алоҳида инвесторларнинг роли ва аҳамиятининг кўтарилиши; қимматли қозғалар бозорининг глобаллашуви ва халқаролашуви.

Калит сўзлар: марказлаштириши, маблағлар концентрацияси, молиявий воситалар, фонд бозори, қимматли қозғалар бозорининг глобаллашуви, *individual* инвесторлар, институционал инвесторлар, Секьюритизация.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ФОНДОВОГО РЫНКА

Аннотация: Прогрессивный рост масштабов мирового рынка акций обеспечивается под влиянием современных мировых тенденций, среди которых сокращение доли коммерческих банков в финансовых активах и рост доли рынка акций и институциональных инвесторов; существенное изменение структуры финансовых инструментов рынка в интересах реального сектора; укрепление взаимосвязи между финансовым и реальным секторами экономики; дальнейшая концентрация и реализация средств; процесс секьюритизации; повышение роли и значения индивидуальных инвесторов на рынке ценных бумаг; глобализация и интернационализация рынка ценных бумаг.

Ключевые слова: Централизация, концентрация средств, финансовые инструменты, фондовый рынок, глобализация фондового рынка, индивидуальные инвесторы, институциональные инвесторы, секьюритизация.

Introduction

The world trend consists of reducing share of commercial banks in financial assets and growth of the share of security institutions and institutional investors, reducing their role in redistribution of financial resources and simultaneous increase in the share of funds distributed through the stock market, on the basis of contractual and collective savings with the use of its tools.

In developed countries, funding costs by issuing securities received preferential development in comparison with the bank loan. At the same time the share of non-bank

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credit institutions in the structure of institutional investors, particularly investment funds is rapidly growing. Simplification of access to the security market, its growth of liquidity led to a partial loss of banks their role as a mediator and main creditor. In the context of everincreasing competition, banks are forced to reconsider their place in financial system, restructure and strengthen investment direction of their activities on the fundamentally new basis.

The objective of the paper was to discuss modern global tendencies of stock market development.

Discussion

Despite the apparent strengthening of the role of security market, two of the financial mechanism of economic growth - through the securities market and by means of a bank loan should not be opposed. The best seems to establish a kind of "division of labor" between them: securities market should be a major source of investment for the purpose of renewal of fixed capital, expansion of production; bank credit can serve as a support mechanism for stabilization of cash flows. Rational correlation, the balance between these two competing mechanisms will not be established immediately-it is a long-term multi factorial process.

One of the key developments became a significant change in the structure of outstanding financial instruments of the market in favor of the instruments of the real sector - corporate securities and their derivatives financial instruments. The result is a steady increase in both absolute and relative terms, the sector of corporate securities (shares and bonds).

There intensify link between financial and real sectors of economy. This trend is stimulated by natural intention for super-profits, exceeding the average rate of profit by reducing the cost of production, higher quality and novelty goods.

It works to improve the rate and yield of securities of corporations and leaders, as a reflection of the degree of efficiency and profitability. The appearance on the market of securities always causes increased interest of large number of investors interested in placing their funds.

Outwardly, this trend is reflected in the fact that industrial companies (newly established) issue securities (shares and bonds) which has become the primary means of mobilizing investment resources. In its turn, mechanism of financial market provides redistribution of funds in favor of the most promising companies that stimulate structural changes in the economy.

Characteristic feature of the present stage of development of security market is further concentration and centralization of capital. The trend towards concentration and centralization of capital has two aspects in relation to the security market:

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- Security market involves all new members and this activity becomes a major, professional;
- The process of allocating major leading market professionals on the basis of increasing their own capital (capital concentration) and their fusion into larger structures of security market (the centralization of capital) which is in progress;

A clear illustration of the last statement is the process of concentration of stock exchange, which took place last decade. The result was total reduction of their number.

There rapidly grow global scale of computerization and technological modernization of financial markets on the basis of modern electronic technology. Computerization has become the basis of the key innovations in the security market (new tools, trading systems, infrastructure).

One of the key trends of security market development at the present stage is associated with the process of securitization. Securitization makes transition of monetary funds from its traditional forms (savings, cash, deposits, etc.) into the form of securities, which facilitate transformation of increasing masses of capital in the form of securities, transformation of one form of securities in other, more accessible to a wide circle investor. Reasons for securitization related, on the one hand, to increasing concentration and centralization of production and capital and increased the role of large companies in financial and real sectors of economy, and on the other - with the objective need to increase liquidity of financial instruments in the context of liberalization and internationalization of financial markets and solving problems cash flow management, which the bank credit is not always able to cope.

As a result of securitization in industrialized countries in the conditions of equilibrium of economy a significant portion of available capital is invested directly in the purchase of securities. There observed tendency to modification forms of savings in the last decades of the last century even in unstable economic environment.

Significant trend is increasing role and importance of individual investors in the securities market. In recent years, a wide range of individual spots in the operations of securities market and possibility of profitable enough to secure placement of their savings, despite some risk factors.

However, it is not only the direct (immediate) investors investing in securities of various companies, but also the indirect investment through a variety of forms of collective investment operating in industrialized countries.

The reliability of securities market and degree of credibility is increasing. Securities market, as well as the entire economy, it is not immune to downturns, crises and other shocks. Moreover, it was the collapse of securities market can serve as an omen of total financial disaster in the state. It is logical that securities markets in many countries have been the object of government regulation.

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Reliability of securities market and degree of credibility on the part of investor's mass is directly related to an increase in the level of organization of the market, the action mechanism of self-regulation and increased government control over it. The scope and value of securities market today is such that it leads to the destruction of the right strain of economic development, the process of reproduction in general.

The state cannot afford itself that trust in this market would be shaken, and masses of people who have invested their savings in securities of the country, or any other, who suddenly lost them as a result of any fraud or upheavals. Therefore, all participants in the securities market are directly interested that it was properly organized and tightly controlled by the most important of his party - state.

However, there is another significant reason for this process - fiscal. Increased degree of organization of the market and control it allows each State to increase its tax base and amount of tax revenue from market participants. At the same time the possibility for overlap "launder" money obtained from illegal businesses and theft.

The most important trend in the development of securities market is its internationalization and globalization. Internationalization of the securities market means that national capital transcends countries, which leads to the formation of global securities market in relation to which national markets are minor.

Investors from any country can invest their surplus funds in securities traded in other countries. Thanks to the computerization of the development of modern means of communication and the use of internet technology stock market takes a global, when national markets are considered as part of a single global securities market.

Globalization of security market as a process of erasing the boundaries between national markets; building a global trading platform, consisting of financial markets in different countries, working in different time zones; integration of financial instruments, market participants, regulators, mechanisms for security transactions - all the key trends in the development of security markets in the last decade of XX century and the beginning of XXI century.

Conclusion

There is a progressive increase in the scale of global security market. Growth of its market capitalization, although the degree of participation in this process developed and developing countries are different and is determined by the specifics of supply and demand factors. Foreign experience shows that the role of security market as a mechanism for accumulation and redistribution of capital in the investment process in modern conditions is increasing.

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QR-Article

PROBLEMS OF BUSINESS ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT IN THE HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SPHERE

Abstract: *In this article, the author studied the problems of business development in housing and communal services, as one of the most important areas of economic reform in Uzbekistan, in particular, its importance for the socio-economic development of territories and sectors of the economy. He also developed proposals to solve problems such as high capital intensity and low labor productivity, an increase in tariffs for housing and communal services, a deterioration in the financial condition of enterprises, a high degree of depreciation of fixed assets, stagnation of the structural development of the housing and communal sphere, and so on.*

Keywords: *housing and communal sphere, capital intensity, labor productivity, tariff, financial condition, depreciation of fixed assets, stagnation.*

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ЖИЛИЩНО-КОММУНАЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЕ

Аннотация: *В данной статье автор изучил проблемы развития бизнеса в сфере жилищно-коммунального хозяйства, как одного из важнейших направлений экономических реформ в Узбекистане, в частности, его значение*

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для социально-экономического развития территорий и отраслей экономики. Он также разработал предложения по решению таких проблем, как высокая капиталоемкость и низкая производительность труда, повышение тарифов на жилищно-коммунальные услуги, ухудшение финансового состояния предприятий, высокая степень износа основных фондов, стагнация структурного развития жилищно-коммунальной сферы и так далее.

Ключевые слова: *жилищно-коммунальная сфера, капиталоемкость, производительность труда, тариф, финансовое состояние, износ основных фондов, стагнация.*

Housing and communal sphere is a technical complex of buildings, structures, engineering networks and equipment, as well as industrial, repair and construction production and maintenance. The result of the functioning of the housing and communal sphere is ensuring the safety and effective use of the housing stock, uninterrupted provision of housing and communal services necessary for human life, further increase in the level of improvement and sanitary condition of the territories of municipalities, and general comfort of living.

The development of market relations in housing and communal sphere is determined by the processes of sustainable development of business structures that are in the phase of active institutionalization. By institutionalization, we mean a complex multi-aspect process with a certain number of stages that ensure the formation of a wide range of entrepreneurship forms that fulfill their inherent target settings, ensuring the satisfaction of the population's demand for housing and communal services within a managed socio-economic system. All this contributes to the integrated development of the territory [1].

A specific feature of the current stage of economic development is the transition to the saturation with business initiative of industries, complexes and sub-complexes of the national economy, which include housing and communal sphere. In our opinion, business in the housing sector is an economic activity carried out by subjects of market relations in order to meet the needs of society for services, to obtain entrepreneurial income necessary for self-development and fulfillment of financial obligations to budgets and other business entities. The currently functioning business structures of housing and communal sphere, which distinguished by both interdependence and sufficient autonomy, and great diversity, divided into three groups [2]:

The first group includes resource-supplying enterprises and organizations that produce material products, namely, water, heat, electricity, the production and consumption of which either coincide in time or follow each other, and therefore enterprises cannot accumulate products and must produce it exactly as much as required in the current period.

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The second group includes housing management organizations, contracting repair, construction and maintenance enterprises, companies.

The third group includes multiservice enterprises and organizations performing work on external improvement, landscaping, collection and disposal of household waste.

Insufficient housing and communal sphere financing for many years has led to the fact that the technical condition of residential buildings, engineering equipment and communications is characterized by a significant level of wear and tear, high accidents, low efficiency of capacities and large losses of energy carriers. Despite the concrete measures taken in recent years, the problem of reproduction of fixed assets of housing and communal sphere has not been resolved [3].

Table 1. Features of the development of housing and communal sphere that determine the growth of business profitability

№	Features	Characteristic
1.	Industry attractiveness	Poorly developed competition and insufficient use of new technologies create conditions for generating additional income
2.	Stability in time	The industry will last forever, the volume of demand is quite predictable, the services are independent of fashion and have no substitutes
3.	Low elastic service demand	If an increase in tariffs leads to a decrease in consumption, then, as a rule, not due to a real decrease in the consumption of services, but due to a more rational attitude to services - the elimination of intra-house and intra-apartment losses
4.	Industry tariff regulation	Can lead to the creation of excess profits for firms if the price of utilities is overpriced
5.	Privatization communal enterprises and attracting to the private business sector	It is supported by the federal policy of market reform of housing and communal sphere, which makes it possible to hope for state subsidies and subsidies within the framework of targeted federal programs. It is interest that prevails for private business.
6.	Opacity consumption and payment volumes	Consumers of many utilities currently not provided with metering devices even by half. In this case, the

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		rate of consumption of services also turns out to be a tool for generating additional income.
7.	Level up trend life of the population	An opportunity is created for the growth of utility bills

One of the aspects of improving the management system for the development of entrepreneurship in housing and communal sphere at the municipal level is the modeling of managerial decision-making processes. In this regard, the simulation model of the housing and communal sphere' cost formation has developed, which makes it possible to make economically sound managerial decisions in the process of price formation. As part of its implementation, a phased selection of indicators characterizing the supply and demand for housing and communal sphere is expected; input of initial data, calculation of indicators and assessment of the results obtained; comparison of alternative options and selection of the optimal one. At the same time, the volume of subsidies and funds attracted to housing and communal services used as an optimality criterion.

The integrated development of business development requires the elaboration of an effective system for monitoring and diagnosing its current state in order to form a system of operational control, through the establishment of adequate feedbacks with the controlled object [4]. This requires the creation of an effective instrumental apparatus, the central link of which, according to the author, should be the integrated system of indicators for monitoring the development of entrepreneurship in the housing and communal sphere market, which he has formed. This system of indicators allows to characterize entrepreneurship in the housing and communal sector according to the main directions of its development.

Based on the above, we have developed the following conclusions and recommendations:

1. Housing and communal sphere are currently in a state of crisis, which is largely caused by objective circumstances associated with the transition from rigid government to a market economy, the government's refusal from the monopoly role of an investor, contractor and owner in the housing sector. The current problems are associated not only with the deterioration of fixed assets, but also with the institutional crisis of the country's housing and communal services system as a whole. One of the main ways to solve the problems that have arisen is the entrepreneurial reform of the industry, which will create a competitive environment and improve the performance of the complex.

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2. Housing and communal sphere of Uzbekistan at the present stage of development has a number of characteristic features that contribute to attracting business to the most promising markets for communal services. Disclosure of the specifics of the industry allows to adjust the mechanism for regulating entrepreneurship in the field of housing and communal services.

3. During the reforming period of the housing and communal sphere market, the contradictory nature of the implementation of state functions in this area was most clearly manifested, reinforced by the impact of systemic crisis trends in the economy. One of the tools for ensuring sustainable development of the housing and communal complex is the formation of a mechanism for the entrepreneurship regulating.

4. The ambiguity of the set goals for the formation of regulating tariffs system for housing and communal sphere and, as a result, insufficient regulatory and methodological support of this process led to serious systemic shortcomings in the regulation of tariffs at the municipal level. The developed simulation model of the formation of the cost of housing and communal services allows to economically select and make management decisions in the process of price formation

5. One of the fundamental factors in the business reform of the housing and communal sphere is the presence of adequate feedbacks with the managed object. The developed system of indicators and algorithm for monitoring the development of business in the housing and communal sphere market, within which the sequence of developing indicators, evaluating and interpreting the data obtained, is presented will help to solve this problem.

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MANAGEMENT AND ITS COMPONENTS IN TOURISM INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract: For individual, tourism is a popular leisure activity. for a city/county tourism has become economy driver. The objective of this paper is to discuss management and its components in tourism activity in Uzbekistan, as these elements affect competitiveness of tourism organizations.

Keywords: tourism, management of tourism industry, elements of tourism products.

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МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ И ЕГО СОСТАВЛЯЮЩИЕ В ИНДУСТРИИ ТУРИЗМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация: Для индивида туризм является популярным видом досуга. для города/округа туризм стал драйвером экономики. Целью данной статьи

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является обсуждение менеджмента и его составляющих в туристической деятельности в Узбекистане, поскольку эти элементы влияют на конкурентоспособность туристических организаций.

Ключевые слова: туризм, управление туристической отраслью, элементы туристических продуктов.

Introduction

Many countries depend on tourism as economy driver. Tourism can be domestic or international. International tourism has both incoming and outgoing implications on a country's balance of payments. The concern generally related to increase revenue from tourism. To be successful on tourism business someone should concern with management. As for individual, tourism is a leisure activity, management should work for tourists experience. This paper was intended to discuss tourism management in Uzbekistan.

Discussion

Tourism as a control object has a number of which are features inherent only to it that are largely due to the specifics of the industry. The task of management is to detect such features in the future to include them in the management of tourism enterprises and organizations. The first feature of tourism in terms of management is a large scale of tourism industry and the complexity of the relationships between its components. The second feature of tourism as an object of control can be considered conflicting and complex definition of objectives of administrative influence. At first glance it may seem that private tourism enterprises targets are clear enough, they are accumulation values, profit earning. However, travel companies often guided by the statement, and not on the actual needs of tourists. To reveal the least, a manager must endeavor, as ineffectiveness of his activities may provoke dissatisfaction of a consumer. It is rather difficult to define clear objectives and criteria for tourist organizations of national, regional, local (city, district) levels, which hampers an objective assessment of their contribution to the development of tourism, forecast and planning activities of such organizations. More complex is a development of individual tourist areas, regions. It is not easy to accurately predict all phenomena and processes occurring in tourism (the changes in the political situation, deteriorating weather conditions, changes in the tax system, etc.), so they often can speak only about the probabilistic nature of forecasts and plans. Thus, tourism is a phenomenon that is difficult to predict and measure. One of the most important features of tourism as a control object is specificity of tourism services and tourism product. They must be considered when designing the system management of tourism enterprises, organizations and territories, in establishing service standards, staff training, etc. Specific requirements for the management district tourism bring and specificity of

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tourist demand, which has a heterogeneous character and stands out among other reasons:

- intangibility and preservation of tourism products;
- diversity of consumer preferences;
- high importance of social factors.

On the management of tourism sector, and this affects its feature as a service in the complex during the stay of tourists on holiday. It is this complex is the basis of the tourist demand. Depending on the customers to the forefront can leave this or that service. Tourism products created by the efforts of many organizations are independent of each other. As a result, it increases the value of cooperation both horizontally and vertically, which facilitates services fall in the complex. Under the influence of a number of objective and subjective factors: climatic, economic, social (free time), demographic, psychological (traditions, fashion), logistical (the development of a network of institutions of accommodation, food, transport, etc.). There formed seasonality of tourism supply and demand. All of these factors, especially climatic conditions determine seasonal fluctuations in demand for tourist services. Their accounting must be the manager of travel agencies to develop a proposal and take action to reduce unevenness in demand for tourist services. Another feature of tourism is the fact that its development affects a much larger number of stakeholders than in any other human activity. Wednesday tourist activity includes customers, suppliers' companies, manufacturers of individual tourist and non-touristic services rulers bodies and agencies, local authorities, social funds, public and other organizations, etc., which affect or may affect it. Tourist organizations cannot be expected from market participants that they will behave the same way. For example, there are certain contradictions between hotel owners, locals and tourists. In addition, interested organizations can be divided into several groups according to the interests of the hotels at the ski resort is probably beneficial reduction of one-day tourism, and the owners of the ski lifts, on the contrary, advantageous to increase the flow of tourists. Even within the same group (for example, among the hotel complexes) traced the various interests. For example, large hotels are usually less interested in offering spa services because they are all necessary for accommodation and recreational visitors at home, and smaller hotels are interested in the travel agency to offer improved resort itself organized action. An important component is relationship between travelers and locals. To reduce the difference to balance the interests of different groups can be at the expense of a balanced plan and coordinate the development of tourism with the participation of stakeholders, guided by generally accepted norms and values. External effects of tourist product can be viewed as the specifics of tourism industry.

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Today, tourism has a significant impact on areas such as economy, ecology, politics, social life, which, respectively also affect tourism. Income from tourism is involved in the local economic cycle and creates an additional (multiplier) effects. Through Tourism there provided employment, created infrastructure, construction of new objects of culture and recreation. Time Tourists create stress on infrastructure, environment, culture and recreation, which may cause dissatisfaction of local residents. If you do not take these negative effects, not to determine ways to overcome them, tourism will not be able to serve as an activator of economy. In this regard, you need to plan and build infrastructure of tourism, with participation of all interested parties and organizations. In addition, there is a certain specificity of dialogue with surrounding tourist.

Everyday life is representative of the tourist housing, work, leisure time, etc. Holidays spent in traveling - is meeting with other travel and locals. The ratio of traveler to him and his motives are determined by how people used to live, to work, it is possible that the organization of free time. As a rule, the more in everyday life one feels limited natural resources, the more it must fulfill certain norms of behavior, the greater the desire to choose to relax unknown country.

Research results indicate that behavior of the tourist impact on the attitude of local people and other travelers. So, if tourists are satisfied with noisy parties, engaged in leisure activities that adversely affect the nature, it causes a negative attitude towards them locals and can spoil the rest.

Finally, tourism management activity is specific and significantly different from the workers of other sectors, although at first it may seem that management of tourism in the region and firms is based on the same basis as management of any enterprise system "man - a man." The essential tasks of managers of tourism are:

- Determining the type of client and identifying its real needs;
- Comparison of the data from the resource potential of travel companies, is clarifying options for addressing these needs with the available tours and itineraries;
- Definition of common trends and patterns of demand, as well as its specific features.

Conclusion

Analysis of features of tourism as a control object shows that the industry is completely different from the others and therefore transferable developments and management model in other areas of labor in the sphere of tourism is impossible.

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ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL IDEAS ABOUT ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Abstract: *Entrepreneurship is certainly considered as the catalyst for the active formation of a market economy, the formation of a competitive market mechanism, and a source of stable economic growth, which is the most important internal strategic factor for sustainable self-development of the national economy. At the same time, entrepreneurship can become a stable source of self-development of the economy only on condition of scientific understanding of its economic essence and content, research of ways of its formation and establishment. Despite the fact that entrepreneurship has passed a long historical path of development, a generally recognized common understanding of this process has not been achieved at the present time. In the article, the author examines the evolutionary formation of scientific and theoretical ideas about entrepreneurship.*

Keywords: *Foreign economic relations, foreign economic relations, foreign trade, globalization, innovation, management, economy of Uzbekistan.*

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АНАЛИЗ НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЙ О ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВЕ

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Аннотация: Катализатором активного становления рыночной экономики, формированием конкурентоспособного рыночного механизма, источником стабильного экономического роста, безусловно, считается предпринимательство, которое является важнейшим внутренним стратегическим фактором устойчивого саморазвития национальной экономики. Вместе с этим, предпринимательство может стать устойчивым источником саморазвития экономики только при условии научного понимания его экономической сущности и содержания, исследования путей его формирования и становления. Несмотря на то, что предпринимательство прошло длительный исторический путь развития, общепризнанного единого понимания данного процесса не достигнуто и в настоящее время. В статье автор рассматривает эволюционное становление научно-теоретических представлений о предпринимательстве.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, малое предпринимательство, предпринимательство, теория предпринимательства, рыночная экономика, саморазвитие, интеграционное развитие.

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TADBIRKORLIK TO'G'RISIDA ILMIY-NAZARIY G'OYALARNI TAHLILI

Annotatsiya: Tadbirkorlik, shubhasiz, bozor iqtisodiyotini faol shakllantirish, raqobatbardosh bozor mexanizmini rivojlantirish, barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish manbai, milliy iqtisodiyotning barqaror o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishning eng muhim ichki strategik omili hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, tadbirkorlik faqat uning iqtisodiy mohiyati va mazmunini ilmiy tushunish, uni shakllantirish va barpo etish yo'llarini tadqiq etish sharti bilan iqtisodiyotning o'zini-o'zi rivojlanishining barqaror manbaiga aylanishi mumkin. Tadbirkorlik uzoq tarixiy rivojlanish yo'lini bosib o'tganiga qaramay, bu jarayon haqida umumiy e'tirof etilgan yagona tushunchaga hali erishilgani yo'q. Maqolada muallif tadbirkorlik haqidagi ilmiy-nazariy g'oyalarning evolyutsion shakllanishini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: biznes, kichik tadbirkorlik, tadbirkorlik, tadbirkorlik nazariyasi, bozor iqtisodiyoti, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish, integratsion rivojlanish.

Introduction

In the context of the modernization of the economy and the development of digital technologies, the issues of state regulation of small business deserve special attention. Entrepreneurship has been an area of intellectual and academic research for many decades. His research is interdisciplinary in nature, as it affects many areas of

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human life. At the same time, scientists have not yet developed a paradigm for the consistent study of entrepreneurship, in particular its structural sectors - small, medium and large.

Literature review

The beginning of the development of the theory of entrepreneurship was laid in the works of representatives of the classical school of political economy R. Cantillon and J.-B. Say, who introduced the category of "entrepreneur" into scientific circulation and focused on his ability to take the risk of inconsistent income and to perform management functions and coordination of production factors. The theory of entrepreneurship was further developed in the works of H. Magoldt, J. Thünen, who considered the uncertainty of the external environment as a source of entrepreneurial income. Representatives of the German historical school (M. Weber, W. Sombart, G. Schmoller and others) interpreted the entrepreneur as an innovator and creator. J. Schumpeter defined the ability to create new combinations of traditional factors of production as an attribute of entrepreneurship.

Further development of the theory of entrepreneurship is associated with the names of F. Knight, who develops the position of the uncertainty of the external environment as a source of entrepreneurial income; J. Shackle, who analyzed the role of time in economic theory; neo-Austrian school (L. Mises, F. Hayek), which analyzed entrepreneurship as a process; D. McClelland, T. Schultz, who studied entrepreneurial motivation, etc.

A significant contribution to the development of the theory of entrepreneurship was made by representatives of the institutional direction, such as T. Veblen, J.C. Galbraith, J. Commons and others. The use of institutional methodology made it possible to reveal the content of the agency contradiction and the essence of the firm as a network of contracts (J. Akerlof, J. Berle, R. Coase, J. Means and others).

Some attempts to integrate the category of "entrepreneurship" with the standard economic model were made in the works of V. Baumol, R. Willigol, J. Panzar, and others. The results of studies of factors affecting the degree of entrepreneurship are presented in the works of K. Dean, S. Thomas et al. The relationship between economic growth and the level of entrepreneurship development was studied using analytical tools of the neoclassical concept, which was reflected in the works of Z. Griliches, E. Mansfield, M. Nadiri, M. Porter, P. Romer, R. Solow and others. ...

Features of the functioning of small business, its impact on the level of innovativeness of the national economy and the rate of economic development were analyzed in the works of G. Berle, P. Weil, D. Gammon, E. J. Dolan, I. Kirzner, D. Lindsay, M. Mescon, I. Maitland, F. Hayek, and others.

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It follows from the above that the theory of entrepreneurship has gone through a long period of development, which made it possible to justify a number of conceptual principles for analyzing the entrepreneurial community.

Research Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was the concept and hypothesis, which formulated the principles of entrepreneurial activity. In the course of the study, works were used in which the theory of entrepreneurship, the theory of innovation and innovative development, the theory of state regulation of the economy, etc. were formulated. The solution of the set scientific problems was carried out using general scientific methods of studying economic processes.

Analysis and results

In our opinion, the essence of small business logically follows from the essence of the basic concept of "entrepreneurship", the scientific evolution of which can be traced through the works of famous classics and contemporaries. Nowadays it is difficult to say who was the first to study this phenomenon. Nevertheless, the founder of the term "entrepreneur" is considered the French scientist R. Cantillon, who in 1725-1730 presented a logically formed general idea about the subject of this phenomenon. According to R. Cantillon, an entrepreneur is someone who takes risks and can legitimately appropriate any income. [1,2]. Subsequently, this concept was clarified and expanded by other scientists. For example, at the beginning of the 19th century, A. Turgot and J. B. Say established the difference between the capitalist and the entrepreneur. According to them, the entrepreneur, accepting risk and acting under conditions of uncertainty, combines the factors of production in new ways, while the capitalist provides his needs with funds [3,4]. At the end of the 19th century A. Marshall in his writings showed the difference between the functions of an entrepreneur and a manager (administrator). He wrote that both perform the functions of organizing and managing production, but the functions of an entrepreneur are broader than those of a manager, since he takes on the risk and full responsibility for the success of the business. A special place in the formulation of the concept of "entrepreneurship" is given to J. Schumpeter. His approach to this phenomenon is purely functional. This is evidenced by the definition he proposed at the beginning of the twentieth century. Entrepreneurs, according to J. Schumpeter, are people who carry out the function of transforming or reconstructing the production system, and they remain so as long as they perform this function. The function of an innovator provides an opportunity for a liberal system to continue to exist without its contradictions [5].

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R. Cantillon, A. Turgot, J. B. Say and J. Schumpeter are considered the founders of the dominant positions in the theory of entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, F. von Hayek, A. Shapiro, R. Khizrich, D. McClelland, P. Drucker and many other scientists who studied various aspects (psychological, managerial, resource) entrepreneurial activity, reflecting the characteristics of the types of economic growth, priorities of economic interests and socio-cultural circumstances in a particular society. So, A. Shapiro saw in the future entrepreneur an individual who is ready to act taking into account previous experience and perception of current opportunities [6]. According to A. Shapiro, an individual's general readiness to create an enterprise arises at the moment when he is dismissed from work. At the same time, the desire to create his own enterprise turns into reality only when the individual sees a convenient opportunity and can collect the necessary funds and other required resources. R. Khizrich, summarizing research on entrepreneurial behavior, revealed that an entrepreneur should be considered only one who demonstrates initiative and creative thinking, who is able to organize social and economic mechanisms for using resources in practice, to accept risk and losses [7]. In turn, D. McClelland suggested using a similar set of characteristics explaining entrepreneurial behavior, such as the need for growth, a moderate propensity to take risks, a preference for vigorous activity, and the acceptance of personal responsibility for success or loss [8].

At first glance, it seems that it is actually impossible to suggest something new in defining the content in this category, since there are countless different interpretations. Nevertheless, relying on the works of modern scientists, we will try to carry out a theoretical analysis of the existing condition and clarify the interpretation of the specific concept of "small business". The reference to the works of scientists of the second half of the twentieth century is explained by the fact that a fundamental reassessment of the role of small business in the economic development of an industrial society took place in the 1970s. The basis for this was the practical refutation of the theoretical paradigm, according to which the ownership of capital is continuously concentrated and enterprises grow in size. Meanwhile, the increase in consumer demand for more differentiated goods has led to industrial reconstruction of two types: the decentralization of enterprises and the formation of associations of new enterprises.

It seems to us that all of the modern views on "entrepreneurship" can be conditionally subdivided into four groups.

The first group should include scientists who regard it as a socio-economic phenomenon that covers a variety of forms of realization of the economic activity of the population, organizational and legal forms of enterprises. At the same time, entrepreneurship is based on the economically independent activity of individuals (legal entities) aimed at achieving socio-economic effect. In reality, entrepreneurship

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is a multidimensional socio-economic phenomenon, covering all spheres of economic activity, and it is based on the economic independence of individuals. The only exceptions are traditional societies and the socialist economic system that commanded in the countries of Eastern Europe and the CIS. We believe, therefore, the authors of some definitions emphasize that entrepreneurship is a market form of management. ... In our opinion, J. Schumpeter would not agree with such a statement, since he believed that a socialist economy in the presence of a “dynamic entrepreneur” could achieve greater efficiency by eliminating non-labor elements [9]. In this context, the phenomenon of the Chinese system of "market socialism" has now taken shape as a separate line of economic research.

The second group can include scientists who refer entrepreneurship as a market form of management. In their opinion, as a form of management, it is based on an extremely rational combination of factors of production, an innovative foundation and is implemented with the aim of generating entrepreneurial income.

In the third group, we put scientists who study entrepreneurship as a specific type of behavior with an innovative component. In their opinion, such behavior is mainly focused on residual income and it is not available to the standard operating agents of the market process.

The fourth group included scientists who consider entrepreneurship to be one of the types of proactive and independent activities carried out at their own risk and under their property responsibility and aimed at generating income. Numerous studies have proved that the initiative to start a new enterprise often manifests itself under the pressure of a situation related to a change in lifestyle, family environment, education, age, professional activity, role models and supportive networks. Some people become entrepreneurs under the influence of negative factors, such as dissatisfaction or job loss, career difficulties.

As a result of generalization and analysis, we found that the substantive part of most definitions describes the main features of entrepreneurial activity. Realization of the fact that the market economy is essentially an economy of entrepreneurship logically leads to the conclusion that the concept under consideration is a socio-economic phenomenon. At the same time, the central figure is the entrepreneur, who is characterized by initiative, independence, innovation, as well as the focus of all his activities on generating income. Traits such as the creative expression of a personality, creative work, a self-organizing subject of the economic process, a system-forming factor of the economic system, also refer to the subject and object of entrepreneurial activity, generally indicating the versatility of the phenomenon under study.

It is well known that the listed features also contain other forms of activity that are not related to entrepreneurship. We see the essence and main difference of

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entrepreneurial activity in the creation of new value with a certain value, and aimed at generating income. Although in this approach there are also differences of opinion. Thus, some scientists believe that the possibilities of creating new value are limited by the boundaries of the entrepreneur's capital resources, namely, by the scale of their human and social capital. Most small businesses produce little and no value, but make a significant contribution to the formation of "social wealth" and jobs [10]. Therefore, for example, V. Baumol proposes to separate the "entrepreneur organizing the company" from the "innovative entrepreneur" [11]. For the first type of entrepreneur, value development may not be as important as intrapersonal changes affecting their area of know-how, network of relationships, or social status. The second type of entrepreneurs carries out a set of sequential actions that ensure the emergence, transformation and use of innovation for the production of new consumer goods, profit, achieving competitiveness through the growth of production efficiency. Obviously, for them, first of all, it is important to implement their own ideas, which, ultimately, are reflected in the inner world of the innovator.

K. Brut and P. Julien, in turn, believe that the types of entrepreneurship are not limited to these two types. In the context of the "individual - creation of a new value" dualism, they distinguish four forms of its demonstration. These are entrepreneurial reproduction, imitation, realization and risk [12]. According to scientists, entrepreneurial reproduction is demonstrated when an individual with extensive experience in a particular field decides to start his own business. At the same time, the entrepreneur creates a slightly new value, which cannot be referred to the category of "innovation". In addition, there will be no internal changes in it.

Entrepreneurial imitation involves the production of the same value, but in a new way (borrowing technology), accompanied by internal transformations in the business entity. This category includes the organization by a large business of a standard restaurant as a result of a radical revision of the direction of business.

If an engineer, previously responsible for innovative projects in large companies, is now developing a new project in a well-studied and promising area for himself, then here is an entrepreneurial implementation. An engineer is considered to have unique knowledge and a network of relationships (customers and suppliers who trust him; potential employees with rare know-how who will follow him without hesitation, etc.). This form of entrepreneurship acts as a source of innovation, where new value is produced through the implementation of the specific qualities of the founder of the business.

World experience shows that entrepreneurial risk is rare, as it is accompanied by a high degree of uncertainty and unpredictability. However, the entrepreneur's innovative potential is fully realized here. At the same time, it is not the potential itself

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that is important, but its difference (between investment in innovation and return; input and output of the system), only in this case there is an effect, a result. If successful, they lead to radical changes in the external environment through the creation of a new distinctive value (usually a new product, and sometimes a new economic sector).

As a result, the first two forms should be attributed to the group of traditional entrepreneurship, and the next two - to innovative entrepreneurship. In its most general form, innovative entrepreneurship is a special, innovative process that leads to the creation of goods (products, services) and technologies that are best in their properties through the practical use of innovations, a constant search for opportunities, an orientation towards innovation, the willingness of an entrepreneur to take all the risks associated with the implementation of a venture project or with the improvement of an existing one, as well as the resulting financial, moral and social responsibility. In the economic literature, there are four main types of innovative entrepreneurship: product innovation; technology innovation; social innovation; management innovation [13].

The main and defining part of all types of innovative entrepreneurship is the creation and production of scientific and technical products, the manufacture of new types of products (goods, services, works, information, intellectual (spiritual) and material values, production technologies, know-how), subject to subsequent implementation.

According to the method of organizing the innovation process in a venture capital company, several main models of innovative entrepreneurship can be distinguished, created on the basis of:

- internal organization, when an innovation is created and (or) mastered within the firm by its specialized divisions on the basis of planning and monitoring their interaction on an innovative project;
- an external organization using contracts, when an order for the development, creation and (or) partial development of innovations, innovations are placed by the firm between third-party organizations, and fully masters them, as a rule, on its own;
- external organization, when the head company for the implementation of venture projects establishes subsidiaries that raise additional funds from external sources.

Additional factors affecting the degree of manifestation and transformation of the above-described forms of entrepreneurship are the type of market (with low, medium or high technology), the investment opportunities of the individual and the state of the external environment (favorable or hostile).

Conclusion

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In general, in our opinion, entrepreneurship is a type of economic management to create new value, carried out on its own initiative, at its own risk and responsibility and aimed at generating income as a result of meeting the needs of counterparties in goods and services. The proposed characterization of the essence of this concept is quite applicable to small business, which is the most widespread form of economic activity in the world, and its boundaries are determined by the scale (coverage) of activities. It is entrepreneurial reproduction and imitation that have found expression in small business in the traditional sense. Entrepreneurial implementation and risk are more inherent in small venture capital firms that carry out scientific and practical research in the development of new products, equipment and technology.

Our proposed definition is consistent with the description of a self-developing and self-sufficient business to create value. At the same time, in practice, most enterprises are formed with the aim of redistributing value and capital flight. In this situation, it is more appropriate to consider entrepreneurship as "the process of discovering and implementing new opportunities for using known resources, discovering new resources, as well as markets for the sale of manufactured products" [14, 15]. Although this definition to some extent reflects the marketing strategy of the entrepreneurial structure in the market.

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QR-Article

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF STATE-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN ROAD AND TRANSPORT COMPLEX OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract: *The article deals with the problem of the implementation of public - private partnership in the road - transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the analysis of international experience, the authors suggested measures to enhance the concession form of public-private partnerships in infrastructure sectors of the national economy of Uzbekistan, on the example of road-transport complex.*

Keywords: *transportation, transportation management, partnership, public-private partnerships, concession activity.*

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5731674](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731674)**O'ZBEKISTON AVTOMOBIL VA TRANSPORT MAJMUASIDA
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGINI AMALGA OSHIRISH
SAMARADORLIGI**

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasining avtomobil - transport sohasida davlat-xususiy sherikligini amalga oshirish muammosi ko'rib chiqiladi. Xalqaro tajriba tahlili asosida mualliflar yo'l-transport majmuasi misolida O'zbekiston milliy iqtisodiyotining infratuzilma tarmoqlarida davlat-xususiy sektor hamkorligining konsepsiya shaklini oshirish chora-tadbirlarini taklif etdilar.*

Kalit so'zlar: *transport, transportni boshqarish, sheriklik, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, kontsessiya faoliyati.*

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**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННО-
ЧАСТНОГО ПАРТНЕРСТВА В ДОРОЖНО-ТРАНСПОРТНОМ
КОМПЛЕКСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА**

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается проблема реализации государственно-частного партнерства в сфере автомобильного транспорта Республики Узбекистан. На основе анализа международного опыта авторами предложены меры по расширению концессионной формы государственно-частного партнерства в инфраструктурных секторах национальной экономики Узбекистана на примере дорожно-транспортного комплекса.*

Ключевые слова: *транспорт, управление перевозками, партнерство, государственно-частное партнерство, концессионная деятельность.*

One of the main problems in the process of modernization and liberalization of socio-economic life of each country is the problem of efficient use of state property. Modern experience of the developed countries shows the possibility of using several methods of managing state property on the basis of market relations. Privatization is one of these methods. But it should be noted that only the privatization of the property does not always produce the expected results. According to experts, in this direction it is necessary to use the advantages of state-private partnerships - another way of effective management of state property.

In modern science, state-private partnership is the institutional and organizational association that occurs between the public and private businesses to implement social

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projects. The system of partnership between the public and private sectors is one of the main components of the mixed economic theory. In practice, this system embodies a certain set of attitudes and institutional environment. The state, in turn, taking responsibility for the formation of the institutional environment is considered as a subject that develops procedures and rules of relationships.

Among well-known forms of state-private partnerships in Uzbekistan corporate enterprises are widespread, they have a legal form as a joint stock company, limited liability company and double liability company.

The authors of this article focus on the future practical application of state-private partnership in the road transport complex of Uzbekistan. However, it would be appropriate to use a phrase such as "property partnership" instead of "state-private partnership." As we know from economic theory, in economy there are only forms of public and private property, or mixed forms. Consequently, relations concerning public and private property, more correctly called "partnership property".

Abroad, there is a type of the implementation of the partnership property, which is called "partial privatization" when the state provides the private business with only part of the material authority. Some forms of presenting state material authority may be a concession, agreement, the agreement on the distribution of products, joint ventures, etc.

Among these forms of property partnerships concession plays significant role, which has been used successfully by many countries as the most appropriate mechanism to establish property relations based on the principles of the market economy.

It should be noted that international experience of using concessions indicates that such agreements are widespread, mainly in the infrastructural sectors, including rail and road sector, in the municipal sector, power, and pipeline transport.

For example, one of the concession projects implemented at the end of the last century in the UK, was a project of Skye Bridge. Skye Bridge - is a 400-meter-long toll bridge connecting the Strait of Loch Alsh in Scotland with the Isle of Skye, the construction of which in 1989 the British government announced a tender. This tender was won by a joint venture Miller-Dywidag, created by companies Miller Civil Engineering (Edinburgh) and Dyckerhoff & Widmann AG (Munich).

Skye Bridge project is considered the first British projects of infrastructure with involvement of PFI (Private Finance Initiative - PFI) according to the agreement signed in 1991 by the Department of Development of the Ministry of Scotland, the UK.

Another project in Hungary is M5 highway. The project provides toll-based operation of the international trade corridor extending from Budapest to the southern border of Hungary, linking Western Europe to the Balkans and Black Sea areas.

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Another feature of this project is that the M5 highway is considered to be a special part of the project, constituting the North-South highway Trans- Europe supported by the UN Economic Commission for Europe, and is part of the 4th transport corridor Pan-Europe (Berlin - Prague - Bratislava - Budapest - Thessaloniki - Istanbul). International tender was declared in 1992 for financing, construction and operation of the highway and in February of the same year the Franco-Austrian-Hungarian consortium, managed by the company Bouygues and Bau Holdings won the tender. Funding for the first phase of the concession was assigned to the company Alfold Koncesszios Autopalaya (AKA), which are the major shareholders of Bouygues and Bau Holdings. The terms of the concession defined prepayment, the composition of tariffs and order of tariff increase.

Given the lack of experience with this form of partnership property in Uzbekistan, the article will discuss the perspectives of concessional agreements in the sectors included in the road transport sector of the Republic, in which public ownership is a priority.

There are a number of reasons for choosing this field as an object of research conducted in this paper. Here are just a few of them: firstly, in Uzbekistan, as well as throughout the world, the need to produce social benefits that serve to meet the growing needs of the population and industries, with each year becomes more urgent; secondly, the increase in production in the complex, in turn, causes congestion of a large number of public resources in the industry; third, the current globalization of the industry, which is included in this complex may provide a connection of the country's economy to international economic relations; fourth, the importance of road transport sector as a sector that produces good, and the priority of state property in it raises the possibility of using the complex forms of property concession agreements.

As it was noted, Uzbekistan pays insufficient attention to the problems of concession activities corresponding concession form of cooperation, which implies economic relations public and private sectors, particularly in the infrastructure sectors. Insufficient knowledge of international experience of imprisonment and state regulation of concession agreements, as well as the lack of research on the problems of the formation of forms of concession activities in our country, issues the challenge before the Sciences of Uzbekistan to strengthen research in this direction.

At first glance it seems that the priority of social approval of state interests in the activity of the complex and continuous excellence for private business interest income deny the intersection of the interests of these two subjects of property. Indeed, the possibility of road transport sector, as a producer of social good, to bring sales revenue - quite a controversial topic. Despite this, we will try to highlight a few areas that allow

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a concession agreement for the participation of the private sector in the activities of the complex.

Firstly, in the process of construction, repair and maintenance of roads can actively engage the private sector. As international experience shows, it is possible to exploit the individual objects of road infrastructure on a fee basis, and this, in turn, will satisfy the need for a material interest of private business. In this regard, it is necessary to develop national standards for the construction of toll roads or reconstruction of public roads taking into consideration the views of international experts.

Secondly, industrial enterprises producing construction materials of the Roads of the Republic, are still state-owned. Since the question of their corporatization is not worth it in the agenda, they can also be for a fixed term to hand over to the concession. At the same time to meet the material interest of the private sector it is required to develop a mechanism to negotiate prices for products produced by these industrial enterprises.

Third, it is possible to use the practice of giving the objects of roadside infrastructure and service on a fixed term on the basis of the concession contract. Of course, due to lack of funds in the complex immediate privatization of such objects seems appropriate, however, it should be noted that the fuller utilization of object of delivery service on some structures of road sector can lead to more efficient use of state property.

In this article, recommendations are developed on the operation of toll roads that did not exist in the history of the road sector in Uzbekistan. This is part of a 886 kilometers to 910 kilometers of the international highway M-39 "Almaty-Bishkek-Tashkent-Termez" passing now through the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

As history of road of Uzbekistan shows, construction of M-39 was launched in 60-70s years of the 20th century. It passes over 658 km through the capital of Uzbekistan, Tashkent city Syrdarya, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Shakhrisabz, Guzar, Dekhkanabad, Sherabad, Angor, connects the capital of the Republic of Kazakhstan Almaty with the Uzbek town of Termez.

Part of this highway passing through the territory of Uzbekistan, crossing the 24 km of the territory of Kazakhstan, re-enters the territory of the country. According to the authors, these 24 kilometers of the highway can be reconstructed on the basis of international requirements and resume movement by transferring the management of the toll road newly created International Corporation.

Calculations show that the reconstruction of this part of the highway M-39 to international toll roads and commissioning required investment funds in the amount of 69960.90 million sums. In addition, repair and maintenance costs of the International Corporation annually amount to about 257.75 million sums.

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If we consider that the average traffic volume at the beginning of line, i.e. passing through Tashkent and Syrdarya region of 26872 vehicles per day, and that on average 65% of the car re-registered in the institution road office Sardob, starting from the border of Kazakhstan, the possible number of passing through the toll road vehicles (potential intensity) will be 17467 vehicles per day).

At the same time, all the roads reaching the highway and leaving it have to be closed, as well as the problem of construction of new, parallel lines, roads for local traffic should be solved. With the parts agreeing on the need for these roads, based on expert judgment, it is necessary to identify the sources of construction financing.

Of course, these calculations and the resulting observational data make it possible to determine the cost of launching the international toll road (Table 1).

Table 1. Efficiency of launching an international toll road

№ number	Activities and indicators	Quantity and unit of measurement	Cost, million sums.
1	Construction of the international road category 1 (4-row, with asphalt concrete covering) with bridges and monolithic concrete walls	24 km	59357,35
2	Installing CCTV devices along roads	In 20 points	19,95
3	Installing anti-freezing devices of the mark «SOPO»	1500 m	1458,6
4	Construction of transitional spaces with the installation of toll system	2	1500
5	Installation of modern scales	2 units	5500
6	Construction of points of service	2 units	375
7	Installation of metal fencing	24 km	1750
8	The cost of repairs and safety of the toll road	24 km	257,75
9	The costs associated with the construction of the road category II (2-row, with asphalt concrete covering)	24 km	13421,1
10	Total expenses		83639,75
11	Traffic	17467 vehicles/day	
12	Daily revenue (tolls 0,04\$/km*24=2400 sum)		41,92

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13	Annual revenue	15301,09
14	Payback period, year	5,47

Thus, according to preliminary estimates the payback period of the international investment project, which makes it possible to return to the continuous operation of the highway M-39 from Tashkent to Termez, is 5.47 years.

For comparison, the payback period in the above-named British project Skye Bridge according to preliminary calculations was 20 years old. Based on the in-service bridge revenues, the payback period had to be reduced to 17 years. Ultimately, investors regained their investment for 4 years earlier than planned, i.e., for 13 years. The terms of the concession project of the Hungarian M5 highway concessionaire provides delivery of state highways in 35 years in good working condition.

In the above calculations the costs associated with the organization of an international corporation are not taken into consideration. In fact, as shown by international experience, the organization of any large international business entity, along with greater complexity than the organization of national companies provide great financial cost.

In our case, it is advisable to organize a corporation in the form of a joint stock company, which is considered by far the most effective organizational and legal form. At the same time 51% of the shares issued by the corporation, may belong to residents of the Republic of Kazakhstan (since the highway M-39 passes through the territory of Kazakhstan), and the remaining 49% - residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Recognizing that the governments of both countries are free to decide the placement of the package of shares, we consider it necessary to underline the feasibility of providing supplies the absolute number of these shares to private business. Of course, in the course of the project the parties may use the opportunity to attract public funds to finance the project through the return of these funds by selling these shares after the private sector, or immediately raise equity capital by selling shares. But in both cases, the relationship will work, involving public and private sectors.

When activated, this part of the toll motorway it is advisable to sign an international agreement between the two countries, as well as recognition by the two states the status of corporation as a participant of legal relations that determine the full responsibility on the territory of the highway.

Summarizing, we can say the following. Implementation of the project, proposed in this paper, which is the first concession project, the organization of which is possible in Uzbekistan, is a more efficient use of transit potential of road transport sector of our country. According to the authors, there are several other projects to increase the attractiveness of the road transport industry for private capital, so the development of

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them considers an urgent task at the present stage of development of infrastructure in Uzbekistan.

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QR-Article

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ISSUES OF TECHNOLOGICAL AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRY

Abstract: *Aspects of the current stage of development of innovations in the world are considered. The directions of development of the innovation sphere in the world until 2030 are analyzed. On the basis of the analysis, the most promising directions for the development of innovative activity in Uzbekistan are identified, which will contribute to the country's transition to a new technological order in the future.*

Key words: *innovation, innovation process, innovation system, technology, economic growth.*

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ВОПРОСЫ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО И ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены аспекты современного этапа развития инноваций в мире. Проанализированы направления развития инновационной сферы в мире до 2030 года. На основе проведенного анализа выделяются наиболее перспективные направления развития инновационной деятельности в Узбекистане, что будет способствовать переходу страны в будущем на новый технологический уклад.

Ключевые слова: инновация, инновационный процесс, инновационная система, технологии, экономический рост.

СANOАТНИ ТЕХНОЛОГИК ВА ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ

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Аннотация: Мақолада дунёда инновацион ривожланишининг ҳозирги босқичи айрим жиҳатлари кўриб чиқилган бўлиб, жумладан жаҳонда 2030 йилгача инновация соҳасини ривожлантириши йўналишлари таҳлил қилинган. Таҳлиллар асосида Ўзбекистонда инновацияларни ривожлантиришининг энг истиқболли йўналишлари аниқланиб, улар келажакда мамлакатнинг янги технологик тартибга ўтишини кўрсатиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: инновация, инновацион жараён, инновацион тизим, технологиялар, иқтисодий ўсиш.

At the present stage of development, the world economy is on the 5th technological order that builds on the achievements in the field of microelectronics, computer science, biotechnology, genetic engineering, new forms of energy, materials, space exploration, satellite communications, etc. There is a transition from isolated firms to a single network of large and small companies connected electronic network based on the Internet, been working in close cooperation in the field of technology, quality control, planning innovation [1]. Currently, according to the prevailing rate of long-term technical and economic development, the technological order is close to the limits of its growth - splash and drop in energy prices, the global financial crisis - a sure sign of the final phase of the life cycle of the dominant technological order and the beginning of economic restructuring on based on the following order. Is being formed today reproductive system of the new, the sixth technological order, the

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emergence and growth of which will determine the global economic development in the next two to three decades [2]. Its contours are only beginning to emerge in the developed world, primarily in the US, Japan and China, and are characterized by targeting the development and application of high technologies ("high-tech"). Sixth technological order will be characterized by the development of robotics technologies based on advances in molecular biology and genetic engineering, nanotechnology, artificial intelligence systems, global information networks, high-speed integrated transport systems — synthesis of the achievements in these areas should lead to, for example, a quantum computer, artificial intelligence, and ultimately provide access to a new level in the systems of government, society, economy. On this basis the main directions of development of innovations for the period up to 2030 will be the world's next priorities [3]:

- Further application of new developments in information and communication technologies in the extractive industries, manufacturing and services;
- Continue to develop new materials for the manufacture of advanced technologies in many industries: electronics, aerospace, automotive, construction industry, etc.;
- Beginning of a breakthrough in the sectors related to human health - biotechnology, diagnostics, treatments, new medicines, patient care, etc.;
- The emergence of entirely new technologies to improve the quality of life, based on the association of nanotechnology, biotechnology, information technology and cognitive science; will be technically possible to significantly expand the biological potential of human, etc.

Period of replacement of technological orders in the leading countries burdened by overcapacity outdated technological order creates for lagging countries a window of opportunity for a technological breakthrough. It thus occurred "economic miracles" of the past century. In recent years, the practice of leading developed and developing countries, there is a shift in focus formation of topics of science and technology towards the search for answers to the so-called Grand Challenges, with which the economy and society will face in the medium and long term.

Among the "base set" of global challenges, formed on the basis of key overseas, the following stand out challenges and trends of the global scale:

- exhaustion of stocks of strategic mineral resources, the search for new sources of energy and energy security;
- an aging population, changing lifestyles of man and society, the growth of socially significant diseases, including cancer and cardiovascular;
- greening the economy and "green growth" associated with the transition to the "carbon" society;
- development of new models of economic development, including the

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transformation of global value chains;

- transition of the global economy to a new stage of technological development, accompanied by a radical change in the sectorial structure and sources (factors) of competitiveness;
- strengthens the role of inter-branch technologies and interdisciplinary studies, including socio-economic and humanitarian.

In the current context of the global of development high-quality sustainable economic growth is possible only on the basis of the concentration of resources on the formation of a new cutting-edge areas of the 6th technological order requiring multiple increase innovation and investment activities. For a country whose economy has a sufficiently diversified industrial structure, the choice of strategy cannot be universal for all industries and sectors. For Uzbekistan, in modern conditions, the optimum direction of the formation and development of NIS should be mixed strategy of innovative development with elements of "borrowing and adaptation of foreign technology and to enhance their own innovative potential".

The most important areas of the emergence and spread of new technologies and the development of innovative activity in the real sector of the economy of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030 should be allocated:

- the development of modern electronics, microelectronics, photonics and electronic instrument;
- creation of modern laser, electron nuclear, ion, plasma, ion-photon processing technologies and new materials;
- creation of high-technology machinery and equipment, instruments, reference tools, methods of measurement and control systems for economic sectors;
- development of biotechnologies based on the achievements of modern genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and bioinformatics, chemical engineering and nanotechnology;
- design and development of new high-performance technologies and devices that use renewable energy (solar energy, hydropower, wind power, bio-energy);
- preparation of nanostructured materials of different functionality from the natural and manmade materials;
- development of high-performance technologies of production of new drugs based on natural (plants, animals, microorganisms, etc.) and synthetic raw materials;
- creation of energy- and resource-saving and environmentally friendly new materials with using nanotechnology;
- and other.

When selecting priorities in the fields of economy of Uzbekistan emphasis should be placed precisely on the trends and technologies that will give the maximum

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effect of increasing the competitiveness of production and social development. Obvious and fundamental points of growth at different stages of NIS should be: firstly, the construction machinery industry, producing innovative equipment, secondly, a high-tech engineering industry that update the equipment at the present level of quality and, thirdly, a special role in this list in a time of global informatization of the world economy must borrow information, communication and connectivity. Thus, there are next industries:

- sub-sectors of mechanical engineering and metalworking (instrumentation, electronics, radio industries, communications, repair of machinery and equipment);
- sub-sectors of medical industry (manufacturing of medical equipment, manufacture of medical devices made of glass, porcelain and plastic, chemical and pharmaceutical industry);
- sub-sector of chemical and petrochemical industry (industry of chemical fibers and threads, etc.).

In this connection the priority areas for the implementation of advanced technologies in the fields of economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan may become:

- Energy, energy- and resource saving. Development and implementation of new energy saving technologies, autonomous sources of heat and electricity, search renewable alternative energy sources (solar and wind, bioenergy). For example: the development and implementation of effective biogas plants for the production of combustible gas and fertilizer from animal waste, crop, specially grown biomass.
- Informatization and ICT. Acceleration of the using processes of new developments in information and communication technologies in the manufacturing and services sectors. Scope of these technologies: for manufacturing parts of any complexity based on digital models, for example, by laser cutting or three-dimensional printers; design automation; "Embedded" computer systems for cars and others.
- Biotechnology. Development of biotechnologies, including in certain areas: biomedical technologies, biopharmaceuticals, food biotechnology, biomedicine, industrial biotechnology and bioenergy.
- Nanotechnologies. Development of methods for creating technologies and devices based on nanotechnology, which are primarily associated with a variety of possible areas of application. For example, the production and the conservation of energy, for example, new fuel elements, inexpensive photovoltaic solar cells etc. ; new materials with predetermined properties, which can be used in virtually all types of economic activities, from cosmetic products to the automotive industry.
- Medicine and Pharmacology. Development and implementation of high-tech production of new drugs based on natural (plants, animals, microorganisms, etc.) and synthetic raw materials.

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▪ Chemical Technologies. Synthesis of polymeric and composite materials with special functional properties, the development of new technologies and means of disposal of radioactive wastes and industrial wastes; chemical aspects of energy, such as the creation of new chemical current sources, the development of technologies for production of fuels from non-oil and renewable raw materials, high-energy substances and materials.

Thus, based on the priorities of economic development, science and technology for the period up to 2030 can be identified strategic priority of innovative technological development aimed at creating a breakthrough in high-tech industries, which will be based on the underlying technologies of 5 technological order and thereby create the conditions and prerequisites to move to the 6 technological order.

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QR-Article

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EXTENDED FRAUD TRIANGLE MODEL: MODERATING EFFECT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND RISK MANAGEMENT

Abstract: *This research used a broaden fraud triangle model by adding two new variables as a moderator which are good corporate governance and company risk management. The samples in this research are direction board of directors and public insurance company commissioners in Indonesia. The application of GCG is measured by GCG index by using worksheet that is published by regulator, whilst implementation of risk management is measured by using risk management index. The hypothesis in this research is examined by using structural equation model to fraud triangle model and Moderated Regression Analysis to influence the moderation from GCG and risk management. Characteristics of a company such as size, insurance sector, as well as board of direction composition and commissioners as another variable which is evaluated its influence partially towards the variable or the relationship between research variables.*

Keywords: *Fraud, Fraud Triangle Model, Theory of Planned Behavior, GCG, risk management.*

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РАСШИРЕННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ТРЕУГОЛЬНИКА МОШЕННИЧЕСТВА: СМЯГЧАЮЩИЙ ЭФФЕКТ КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РИСКАМИ

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Аннотация: В этом исследовании использовалась расширенная модель треугольника мошенничества путем добавления двух новых переменных в качестве модератора, которые являются хорошим корпоративным управлением и управлением рисками компании. Образцами в этом исследовании являются совет директоров дирекции и уполномоченные государственных страховых компаний в Индонезии. Применение GCG измеряется индексом GCG с использованием рабочего листа, опубликованного регулирующим органом, в то время как внедрение управления рисками измеряется с помощью индекса управления рисками. Гипотеза в этом исследовании проверяется с помощью модели структурных уравнений для модели треугольника мошенничества и регрессионного анализа с модерированием, чтобы повлиять на модерирование со стороны GCG и управления рисками. Характеристики компании, такие как размер, сектор страхования, а также состав совета директоров и уполномоченных в качестве еще одной переменной, которая частично оценивает ее влияние на переменную или взаимосвязь между переменными исследования.

Ключевые слова: Мошенничество, Модель треугольника мошенничества, Теория запланированного поведения, GCG, управление рисками.

Introduction

Fraud problem becomes a center of attention when there is a global financial crisis which starts in 2007. [Stanton, 2011] states that company management fails to protect the ownership and as a stakeholder in company. That failure makes the company realize of the importance of good corporate governance to anticipate and predict similar events in the future. Insurance corporate governance has an important role to convince and gain trust from the stakeholders, especially consumers and investors, that insurance company has been managed based on transparency, fairness, accountability, responsibility, and independency.

[Richins, 2014] states that fraud is one of the main failure causes which decreases the company image, especially in the last ten years. There are some special ways which can be done by the company to decrease and omit that fraud. Hiring internal or external auditors, creating cultural etiquette, implementation of computer programs, using whistleblower, management surveillance in micro level, fixing package for employee's compensation, as well as giving out sanctions or punishments towards any kinds of fraud. According to Lin et al, fraud in a company creates a financial hindrance in the means of a company that experience fraud shows sensitivity towards a positive cash flow after the fraud occurs. The result of this research shows that fraud may have a concrete impact towards the company performance through the impact on external financial expenses and internal cash authority. Fraud in financial report is still a huge problem although there is a legislative effort and study from [Odom and Ugrin, 2014] which helps in identifying how to rationalize a

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fraud, when the consequences can be anticipated, as well as why the prevention is ineffective.

[Haithem et al., 2014] states that the cause of fraud is not universal and its impact towards the involvement of fraud is probably influenced by cultural factor in a wide range of levels, society level which leads to individualism dimension or collectivism, as well as idiocentrism/allocentrism which is cultural conceptualism level as individual. Thus, the understanding towards a wide range of cultures in the fraud will enrich knowledge about how and why the fraud may occur, how the fraud can be detected, and how the fraud can be controlled. According to [Cumming et al., 2011], current research about the fraud indicating factors in the companies in developing countries, mainly is focused on the mechanism of internal governance and a small part of them is about the impact of the presence of external party, such as involving an analyst. [Biljanoska, 2015] mentioned that implementation of risk management system in general is the base of detecting and preventing fraud.

[KNKG, 2009] states that insurance company is a company which promises protection towards the consumers and or people who have the polis as well as gathering people funding. Both of these roles experience a rapid growth which therefore requires insurance company that is strong and reliable. Insurance industry which consists of insurance company, reinsurance company, and supporting insurance company which operate in sharia system, must uphold insurance principles especially utmost good faith principle and good corporate governance implementation to fulfill the responsibility as promised. GCG must be understood as well by the stakeholders hence the insurance industry can develop better.

The implementation of risk management effectively has an aim to ensure that the risk can be understood, managed, and if necessary, can be communicated to the stakeholders. The implementation of risk management is getting more popular in many kinds of economy sector, especially in financial institution which is a trigger as well as the most severe part that receives major impact of global financial crisis. [OECD, 2014] states that a huge surprise from the global financial crisis is the failure in implementing risk management in a company. One of the consequences which have a massive impact is financial fraud which occurs in the companies, even in the top-level management. This matter is strongly related with business etiquette problem and also breaks the trust of stakeholders. This fraud is even affecting the bankruptcy of companies and lawsuits in several corporate which operate in international level.

Two main factors which are considered to decrease the fraud risk in insurance industry are the implementation of good corporate governance and risk management of insurance companies. However, in this condition, the implementation of GCG and risk management in Indonesian insurance industry is relatively new if it is seen from

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the OJK new regulations which have been published only in the last two years, which are in 2014 and 2015. This condition shows that GCG implementation and risk management relatively are not yet implemented entirely and in general in insurance industry. Hence, it is predicted to have an impact on identification attempt and fraud risk management.

Identification of fraud risk and its management can be seen from the perspectives of board of directors and commissioners from public insurance company in Indonesia. Implementation of GCG in insurance industry in Indonesia relies on the regulation of GCG which is released by Otoritas Jasa Keuangan (OJK). Implementation of risk management in insurance companies also relies on the regulation of OJK as well as the issued letter about the risk of insurance company evaluation. The risk evaluation process is measured by perception from board of directors and commissioners, including the evaluation towards the fraud risk which is experienced or encountered in the company.

The aim of this research is to obtain information or a valid data which is reliable and based on the facts also empirical data that can be explained as: (1) To know and analyze if the principles of corporate governance is good, which consists of accountability, transparency, responsibility, independency, and fairness, influencing towards the fraud in insurance industry, and (2) to know and analyze if the implementation risk management process, which consists of risk identification, risk analysis, evaluation, and risk management influence a decrease in number of frauds in insurance industry.

Literature Review

Fraud Triangle Model

According to The Institute of Internal [of Internal Auditor, 2009], the understanding of fraud is:

Any illegal act characterized by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust. These acts are not dependent upon the threat of violence or physical force. Frauds are perpetrated by parties and organizations to obtain money, property, or services; to avoid payment or loss of services; or to secure personal or business advantage

In the insurance context, National Association of Insurance Commissioners (NAIC) states that insurance fraud happens when the insurance company, agent, and loss evaluation, as well as consumers do fraud intentionally to gain an advantage which is illegal.

Fraud Triangle Model is first stated by Donald R. Cresses in 1973 and becomes one of the research models that is used as a reference and continues to develop until present time. [Mackevicius and Giriunas, 2013] explain that the model transformation seems like this figure below.

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According to [of Internal Auditor, 2009], fraud risk evaluation generally consists of three main steps which are: (1) Fraud risk factors identification which are relevant, (2) Potential fraud scheme identification and creating its priority based on its risk level, (3) Surveillance mapping that exists in order to find the potential fraud scheme and to identify the inequality, (4) examining the effectiveness of operational fraud prevention and detection surveillance, and (5) documentation and report of fraud risk evaluation. Prevention process and fraud risk detection can be seen in the figure below:

Research done by [Aghghaleh et al., 2014] used the fraud triangle model from financial and management perspective which analyzes the relationship between companies experience in fraud with factors such as sales to credit ratio, debts to assets ratio, the total number of auditing committee, and total number of board of directors. Some researchers that use that model is [Boulter et al., 2013] who use the statistic approach, which is the regression analysis, to know the financial factors and management structural which affect the experience of the company's fraud occurrence in Malaysia.

Figure 1: Fraud Triangle Model Evolution [Mackevicius and Giriuнас, 2013]

Figure 2: Prevention, detection, and fraud investigation [of Internal Auditor, 2009].

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Good Corporate Governance

According to [Kostyuk et al., 2007], the term of “Corporate Governance” can be interpreted as narrow and broad which are connected with two perspectives, which are shareholders and stakeholders. In the narrow perspective, governance is a relationship between company managers, board of directors, and shareholders. While in broad perspectives, governance includes combination of laws, regulations, share issuance regulation, and practices in managing private companies in which the company attracts capital, operates efficiently, and generates profits, as well as fulfilling responsibility and people’s expectation.

[Claessens, 2003] states that the understanding governance can be classified into two groups. First group emphasizes on the behavior patterns which are actual behavior of companies in different measurements, such as performance, efficiency, growth, financial structure, and treatment to the shareholders and stakeholders. The second group emphasizes on the normative working framework which are regulations whereas a company that operates are from law system, judicial system, financial markets, and labor market.

Referring to World Bank, the governance of a company consists of four pillars which are accountability, fairness, transparency, and responsibility. Accountability assures that management ranks are responsible to the board of directors, and board of directors is responsible to the shareholders. Fairness pillar protects the rights of shareholders, treating every shareholder in fairness and justice, including the minority of shareholders. Transparency pillar assures the rate and accuracy of revealing important information, including financial situation, performance, ownership, and governance. The last pillar is responsibility which understands the rights of shareholders and encourages cooperation between companies and stakeholders in order to create welfare, employment, and economy sustainability.

The governance principles according to OECD briefly includes:

- (1) Ensure that basic working framework of governance is effective;
- (2) Rights of shareholders and functions of controlling shareholders;
- (3) Fair treatment towards the shareholders;
- (4) The role of shareholders in corporate governance;
- (5) Revealing and transparency;
- (6) Directors responsibility.

In OECD 2004, it is stated that: “working framework of company governance must encourage transparency and efficient market, along with the laws and regulations, and divides clearly the responsibility and obligation between the authorities which conduct surveillance function, regulations, and law enforcement.”

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Figure 3: Conceptual framework by [Haithem et al., 2014]

OJK regulation explicitly regulates risk management or risk management implementation which is in Peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 2/POJK.05/2014 about good corporate governance for insurance companies. A good corporate governance is a structure and process that is used and implemented in insurance industry to increase target of profit and to optimize the value of a company for all the stakeholders

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especially the polis holders, participants and or other parties that gain benefit, in terms of accountable and in regards to the values in law as well as etiquette values.

Risk Management

The understanding of risk management in terms of editorial differs from one institution to another, even though in terms of substantive, it is relatively similar. Some understandings of risk management from international institution are as follows:

1. General management functions which identify, evaluate, and manage the cause and effect from uncertainty and risk from organization. (LOMA)
2. Identification, analysis, and risk management which may threaten operation, asset, and other responsibilities from an organization. (CII)
3. Risk management of a company is a process, which is influenced by board of directors, management, and other personals, implemented in strategy implementation as well as to include entire company, designed to identify potential events that may affect business entity, as well as to manage risks as in the estimated risk which is expected by the company to provide proper assurance with the reach of company goal. (COSO)
4. Systematic process through understanding, evaluation, and risk management to maximize the opportunity to reach the goal and assure the organization, individual, and people. (IRM)
5. The coordinated events to direct and control organization as in line with the risk. (ISO 31000)
6. Process whereas an organization in every industry evaluates, controls, exploits, uses, funds, or surveys the risk from all the resources with the aim of increasing short-term value and long-term value from organization from stakeholders. (CAS)

The understanding of risk management for an insurance company in Indonesia refers to OJK (2014) which is:

The series of procedures and methodology which are used to identify, measure, survey, control the risk may appear from the event in non-bank financial services institutions.

In the year of 2010, three associations - AIRMIC, ALARM, and IRM - together do a completion of company risk management steps which has been arranged in 2002 and is adjusted as standard of ISO 31000. The steps of risk management that have been adjusted with the standard of ISO can be seen as follows:

[Ciorciari and P, 2008] states that the conduction of company risk management framework (ERM/Enterprise Risk Management) encourages and increases the awareness of risk in every management level in a company, from strategic to operational level, and from top management to the employees. Referring to [COSO, 2004]. ERM is a process of risk management of a company, which is influenced by

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board of directors, management, and other personals, implemented in strategy implementation as well as to include entire company, designed to identify potential events that may affect business entity, as well as to manage risks as in the estimated risk which is expected by the company to provide proper assurance with the reach of company goal.

Figure 4: A Structured approach to Enterprise Risk Management [AIRMIC, 2010]

Proposed Research Model

The method that is used in this research is survey method and data collection which aims to know and determine the temporary position of the variables - the evaluated variables are based on the data during the research and connecting between variables that are evaluated. The data sources are from all the board of directors and commissioners in public insurance companies in Indonesia which is by filling in a questionnaire and GCG index and risk management index by top leaders in public insurance company.

The implementation of good corporate governance uses the GCG index that is issued by regulators in Indonesia. The risk management is measured by index that is developed by Monde and Girogino by using several questions that are classified into three fields which are: (1) Risk Cultural, (2) organization, and (3) process. Risk management index measurement uses 22 closed questions which therefore the score will be 0 as the lowest and 100 as the highest. This research model will rely on the fraud triangle model which is developed by [Harrison, 2014]. Fraud triangle model is added with GCG variable. Risk management in insurance companies and public insurance company's characteristics as moderator. The suggested research method can be seen below:

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Figure 5: Proposed Research Model

Statistic technique that is used in the model examination or research hypothesis is Structural Equation Model and Moderated Regression Analysis.

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QR-Article

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ANALYSIS OF INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM ON FINANCIAL STATEMENTS GOVERNMENT OPINION

Abstract: *Accountability, transparency and reliability of financial reporting is key in reaching Opinion WTP. implementation of internal control in government agencies, in the National Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMN) 2010-2020 SPIP implementation be used as one indicator of mainstreaming good governance, which must be implemented by each agency and became an operational basis for the entire implementation of development, an effective system of internal control in each government agency used as a priority activity area of the state apparatus (in RPJMN 2010-2020) conducted by BPKP. This study is qualitative research. This study illustrates what is causing the government gets opinions Fair With Exception (WDP). Results of this study are expected to provide input to the report's authors to be able to present the audit report in accordance with the criteria set by the CPC. While SPIP is a system of internal control that is held in the whole central and local government. Elements of Internal Control System (SPI) in PP-SPIP refers SPI elements that have been practiced in government in various countries, which include five elements 1) control environment (8 sub-elements), 2) risk assessment (2 sub elements), 3) control activities (11 sub-elements), 4) information and communication (2 (3 sub elements).*

Keywords: *control, system, financial, opinion.*

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АНАЛИЗ СИСТЕМЫ ВНУТРЕННЕГО КОНТРОЛЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ МНЕНИЕ ПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВА

Аннотация: Подотчетность, прозрачность и надежность финансовой отчетности являются ключевыми в достижении мнения WTP. Внедрение внутреннего контроля в государственных учреждениях, в Национальном среднесрочном плане развития (RPJMN) на 2010-2020 гг. Внедрение SPIP должно использоваться в качестве одного из показателей внедрения эффективного управления, которое должно быть внедрено каждым агентством и стало оперативной основой для всего процесса разработки, эффективная система внутреннего контроля в каждом государственном учреждении, используемая в качестве приоритетной области деятельности государственного аппарата (в RPJMN 2010-2020 гг.), проводимой НСРПР. Это исследование является качественным исследованием. Это исследование иллюстрирует, что является причиной того, что правительство получает справедливые мнения с исключением (WDP). Ожидается, что результаты этого исследования послужат вкладом для авторов отчета, чтобы они могли представить аудиторский отчет в соответствии с критериями, установленными СРС. В то время как SPIP - это система внутреннего контроля, которая проводится во всех центральных и местных органах власти. Элементы системы внутреннего контроля (SPI) в RP-SPIP относятся к элементам SPI, которые практиковались в правительстве в разных странах, которые включают пять элементов: 1) среда контроля (8 подэлементов), 2) оценка рисков (2 подэлемента), 3) контрольная деятельность (11 подэлементов), 4) информация и связь (2 (3 подэлемента)).

Ключевые слова: *контроль, система, финансы, мнение.*

Introduction

The creation of financial performance accountability is an absolute thing manifested by a regional leader. It is implicit in the Act (Act) No. 17 of 2003 on State Finance, Law number 01 of 2004 on State Treasury, and Law number 15 of 2004 on the Audit of the Management and Financial Responsibility State. Article 31 paragraph (1) Act No. 17 of 2003 states the Governor / Regent / Mayor submitted a draft local regulation (regulations) on the accountability of the budget to Parliament in the form of financial statements, audited by the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) not later than 6 (six) months after the fiscal year ends. 'm Article 31 paragraph (2) of Law No. 17 of

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2003 states the financial statements include budget realization report, Balance Sheet, Cash Flow Statement and Notes to the Financial Statements, accompanied by the local government financial reports. One concrete efforts to achieve transparency and accountability in public finance management is the submission of the financial statements that meet the government's principles on time which is based on the government accounting standards. Namely Government Regulation (PP) No. 24 of 2005 on Government Accounting Standards.

Realize accountability and transparency in governance is not as easy back your hand, required an sub-elements), and 5) monitoring of internal control intensive effort undertaken on an ongoing basis. In 2008 the Government issued Government Regulation No. 60, 2008 concerning the Government Internal Control System (SPIP). Designing PP was initiated by the Finance and Development Supervisory Agency (BPK) as the implementation of Article 58 paragraph (2) of Law No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury. SPIP aims to provide reasonable assurance for achieving effectiveness and efficiency in achieving the objectives of the governmental activities, the reliability of financial reporting, safeguarding of state assets, and compliance with laws and regulations. With the PP-SPIP then every minister / head of the institution, governors, regents / mayors shall exercise control over the implementation of the activities of government based on the SPIP as stated in Article 2 paragraph (1), and also responsible for the effectiveness of internal control systems in the each. Chairman of the CPC at the time, Anwar Nasution, a positive response to the issuance of PP-SPIP by saying that the PP has been long-awaited CPC. One reason why the CPC many times to give an opinion or a disclaimer does not provide an opinion on the financial statements of the central government (Audited) partly because of the inadequacy and lack SPIP institutionalized.

Internal Control System (SPI) is an implementation of the monitoring phase contained in the budget cycle (budget cycle) consisting of:

- 1) Stage budgeting,
- 2) Budget approval stage,
- 3) Stage of implementation of the budget,
- 4). Phase pegawai budget execution,
- 5) Phase ratification budget calculations.

Under Law No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury, President as head of government was given the mandate to organize and conduct the internal control system within the government as a whole in order to improve performance, transparency, and accountability in financial management. On the basis of these rules, on August 28, 2008 the government issued Government Regulation No. 60 of 2008 concerning the

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Government Internal Control System (SPIP). PP No. 60/2008 further provides direction on how to implement the concept and the SPIP.

This paper aims to determine the extent of influence of the reliability of the Government Internal Control System (SPIP) has been implemented, the relationship between subjective statements of SPIP with external control apparatus, and the factors that influence the increase or decrease in the quality and presentation of financial statements through a subjective statement of CPC.

Research Method

This study is qualitative research. This study illustrates what is causing the government gets opinions Fair with Exception (WDP). Results of this study are expected to provide input to the report's authors to be able to present the audit report in accordance with the criteria set by the CPC.

Secondary data used were obtained from a third party such as the Internet, newspapers, and articles. Analysis of documents or content analysis is a method that includes the collection of data and information through testing records and documents. Secondary data were obtained from the Supreme Audit Agency in the form of Statements Audit Reports Government finances.

Discussion

Government Regulation No. 60 of 2008 has been a standard or reference in implementing governance and financial accountability, the implementation of the budget. In Article 56 paragraph (4) of Law number 01 of 2004, declared Local Government Finance Report (Government) should be prepared based on the system of internal control (SPI). The role of SPI is to improve performance, transparency, and accountability in the financial management of the State. President as head of the government regulating and organizing the internal control system within the government as a whole. The purpose and objectives of the government set PP No. 60 of 2008 on the system of internal control government (SPIP) is to improve the quality of financial reporting transparency and accountability of local government as a supporter of the financial statements of the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK). Article 15 paragraph (1) of Law Number 15 of 2004 states the examiner (CPC) prepared a report on the results of the examination (LHP) after the examination is completed and Article 16 paragraph (1) of Law Number 15 of 2004 states that the examination report on the government's financial statements containing opinions. Opinion is a professional statement to the conclusion the results, the level of fairness of the information presented in the financial statements of local governments.

BPK audit results in the form of a report of investigation (LHP) and giving opinions on the fairness of presentation of financial statements. In conclusion the

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results: a) Unqualified (WTP), b) Naturally, With Exception (WDP), c) Not Fair (TW) d. disclaimer. PP No. 60 of 2008 concerning the Government Internal Control System, SPI is an integral process in actions and activities performed on a continuous basis by the management and all employees to provide reasonable assurance on the achievement of organizational goals through effective and efficient, the reliability of financial reporting, security state assets, and compliance with laws and regulations. While the Government Internal Control System (SPIP) is the Internal Control System as a whole held at the central and local governments.

Government Regulation (PP) No. 8 of 2006 on financial reporting and the performance of government agencies, SPI is a process that is influenced by management designed to provide sufficient confidence in achieving effectiveness, efficiency, compliance with laws and regulations, and the reliability of the presentation Government's financial statements. The relationship between subjective statements of SPIP with external control apparatus, CPC as a functional unit extern officers have the authority to conduct an audit to account for the reliability of the financial management responsibilities of local government, based on the Internal Control System has been implemented by the Government of the head region. In Article 2, paragraph (3) Regulation No. 60 of 2008, SPIP goal is to provide reasonable assurance for achieving effectiveness and efficiency in achieving the objectives of the state government, the reliability of financial reporting, safeguarding of state assets, and compliance with laws and regulations. A SPIP said to be good if it meets the five elements of Internal Control System (Sudjono and Hoesada, 2009) which include:

1. Environmental control of the government agencies that influence the effectiveness of in-ternal control.
2. Risk assessment on the possibility of events that threaten the achievement of the goals and objectives of government agencies.
3. Control activities to address the risks and the establishment and implementation of policies and procedures to ensure that the measures address the risks have been effectively implemented.
4. Information and communication. Information is data that has been processed can be used for decision making in the course of the duties and functions of government agencies. Communi-cation is the process of delivering a message or information to use a particular symbol or emblem either directly or indirectly, to obtain feedback.
5. Monitoring of internal control over the perfor-mance of SPI and processes that provide con-fidence that the findings of audits and other evaluations followed up immediately.

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Internal Control System (SPI) in the reporting entity (local government) is a factor that determines the reliability of the financial statements of the entity. Therefore, in giving an opinion on the fairness of financial statements diauditnya, auditors confidence in the effectiveness of the controls laid. Similarly, the BPK auditors in carrying out their assignment should be supported by an understanding of the internal control of a local government for planning audit (Mulyadi, 2002). Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 4 of 2008 on guidelines for the implementation of the review of the financial statements of governments, SPI is a process that is influenced by management designed to provide sufficient confidence in achieving effective-ness, efficiency, compliance with laws and regulations, and the reliability of the presentation financial statements.

The auditor's understanding of internal control are used for

- 1) The possibility of whether or not the audit conducted,
- 2) Potential material misstatements that may occur,
- 3) Risk detection,
- 4) The design of substantive tests.

Assessment of the SPI is useful to identify the management procedures that have a regional financial risk for the occurrence of a material misstatement in the financial statements. Assessment of the SPI made by parties who have the authority as a unit supervisor intern and extern auditor (inspector or BPKP) and auditor (CPC).

Procedures for assessing the SPI made through the following process:

a) Understanding financial management systems and procedures covering areas: Systems and Procedures Cash Receipts; Cash Expenditure Systems and Procedures; Accounting Systems and Procedures Unit; Accounting Systems and Procedures Regional Financial Management Officer (PPKD); Systems and Procedures Preparation of Financial Statements.

b) Observation and/or interviews with stakeholders in each procedure. This activity is to identify the risks that may arise in each sub-process and the presence of existing control system in order to anticipate the risks concerned.

c) Do an analysis of the risks that have been identified to a conclusion about the possibility of a material misstatement in the financial statements. d) Do an analysis of the risks that have been identified to a conclusion about the direction of the implementation of SPI testing.

Effectiveness of internal control systems of government (SPIP) is the responsibility of the leadership of the Institute / Governor / Regent / Mayor. Includes the following activities:

a) Internal control over local governance, duties and functions of the agency, including financial accountability. Committed by the internal watchdog of government

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(APIP) through audit assignment, review, evaluation, monitoring, and other monitoring activities.

b) SPI implementation of government guidance. Under the terms of the legislation, through the preparation of technical guidelines SPIP implementation, dissemination, education and training, coaching and consulting, and increase the competence of auditors. The relationship between subjective statements of SPIP with external control apparatus, CPC, the effectiveness of Internal Control System is determined by the commitment of Government of each head of the institution / Governor / Regent / Mayor in complying with laws and regulations of management of local finance, the conclusion that the results of the examination conducted by CPC, can be a subjective statement includes a. Unqualified (WTP), b. Naturally, With Exception (WDP). c. Not Fair (TW) and d. disclaimer.

Conclusion

With the issuance of Government Regulation No. 60 of 2008, each government agency is obliged to apply the SPIP in its activities. Application SPIP properly will improve the image of government being able to achieve its goals effectively and efficiently, featuring reliable financial reporting, and prevent the state from loss because it has the human resources to obey the rules. There are five elements of leadership SPIP requiring government agencies to have certain competencies and perform certain tasks. For that, it's time to prepare the entire leadership of government agencies and organizations that led him to apply SPIP.

The presence of SPIP is a step forward considering that there is no minimum guideline for government agencies at the time of going to design internal control. Internal control system (SPI) in PP- SPIP interpreted as an integral process in actions and activities performed on a continuous basis by the management and all employees to provide reasonable assurance on the achievement of organizational goals through four pillars, namely

- 1) effectiveness and efficiency of achievement of objectives,
- 2) the reliability of financial reporting,
- 3) security of state assets,
- 4) compliance with laws and regulations.

While SPIP is a system of internal control that is held in the whole central and local government. Elements of Internal Control System (SPI) in PP-SPIP refers SPI elements that have been practiced in government in various countries, which include five elements:

- 1) control environment (8 sub-elements),
- 2) risk assessment (2 sub elements),

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- 3) control activities (11 sub-elements),
- 4) information and communication (2 sub-elements),
- 5) monitoring of internal control (3 sub elements).

For the realization of a powerful and effective SPIP, the five elements SPIP should be applied in an integrated and integral part of the activities of government agencies. The application is intended to be integrated all the elements are applied, starting from the development of the control environment elements (8 sub-elements), to the elements of internal control monitoring (3 sub elements).

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ЭЪЛОН

Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисоаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E - library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

“Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” ISSN 2181-2357 электрон журнали ҳам ўз фаолиятини бошламоқда. Бизнинг журналда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссиясининг қуйидаги ихтисосликлари физика-математика, кимё, биология, геология-минералогия, техника, қишлоқ хўжалиги, тарих, иқтисодиёт, фалсафа, филология, география, юридик, педагогика, тиббиёт санъатшунослик, архитектура, психология, социология фанлари бўйича миллий ва хорижий

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муаллифларнинг фанлардан эришган ютуқлари ва истиқболлари борасидаги илмий мақолалари, илмий тадқиқотлар олиб бораётган олимларнинг илмий изланишлари натижалари эълон қилинади. Электрон журнал ҳар ойда бир марта эълон қилинади.

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5731674](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731674)**ВНИМАНИЕ ОБЪЯВЛЕНИЕ!**

Уважаемые коллеги! Сообщаем вам, что издательский дом «AL-FARGANUS» и «**Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali**»- «Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований» начали свою деятельность на рынке образовательных услуг Узбекистана.

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